

D6.5 Third Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
CAPS	Collective Awareness Platforms
CAPSSI	Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation
COMRADES	Collective Platform for Community Resilience and Social Innovation during Crises
D5.3	D5.3 Second version of the COMRADES platform
D6.1	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan
D6.3	D6.3 Initial Exploitation Plan
D6.4	D6.4 Second report on Communication and Dissemination Activities
D6.5	D6.3 Third report on Communication and Dissemination
D6.6	D6.6 Final Exploitation Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
Gov2u	Government To You
HDX	Humanitarian Data Exchange
iHub	iHub Ltd
Mx	Month x
NGO	Non-Government Organization
OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OU	Open University
Tx.y	Task x.y
TUD	Delft University
UN	United Nations
USFD	University of Sheffield
WP	Work Package
Yx	Year x

Executive summary

The current document under the title D6.5 “Third Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities” is a yearly report on the communication and dissemination activities implemented by the COMRADES project during its third year (*January 2018 – December 2018*). Particularly, it addresses two main aspects: a) the communication tools (*website, social media, e-newsletter, digital publishing platforms etc.*) that the consortium employed and the actions that were undertaken by using these tools within year 3, and b) the communication and dissemination activities performed such as workshops and conferences organized by the COMRADES, participation in third party events, media coverage, publications and so on.

D6.5 is a public deliverable of this project, part of the WP6, and consists of an update of D6.4 “Second report on Communication and Dissemination activities” that was submitted to the European Commission in M24 (*December 2017*). Information concerning the project’s scope and objectives as well as WP6 is also presented in order to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the Description of Action (DoA), and the other WP6 deliverables is requested from the reader. Overall, it is based on, and is consistent with, the DoA and the GA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

1 Introduction

1.1 The project

COMRADES project was launched in January 2016 with a lifetime of 36 months and it aims to empower communities with intelligent socio-technical solutions to help them reconnect, respond to, and recover from crisis situations.

COMRADES consortium is building a new generation, intelligent resilience platform to provide high socio-technical innovation and to support community resilience in crises situations. The platform will capture and process in real-time, multilingual social information streams from distributed communities, for the purpose of identifying, aggregating, and verifying reported events at the citizen and community levels. Resilience frameworks, guidelines and best practices will be embedded into the platform design and functionality, and enriched with open datasets and open source software.

The main objectives of the project are to foster social innovation during crises for safeguarding communities during critical scenarios from inaccurate, distrusted, and overhyped information, and for raising citizen and community awareness of crisis situations by providing them with filtered, validated, enriched, high quality and actionable knowledge. Community decision-making will be assisted by automated methods for real-time intelligent processing and linking of crowdsourced crisis information.

1.2 WP6 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

This work package provides the overall coordination effort for dissemination and exploitation, and communicating the project to external parties. It will proactively plan, execute, and report all relevant activities, and ensure that COMRADES engages fully in collaborative events such as international conferences and builds appropriate partnerships with other CAPS projects, and will facilitate collaboration with external bodies in Europe and standards bodies.

There will be a particular focus on building the community of COMRADES researchers, and connecting with the developers and user communities of crises resilience platforms. WP6 will work with other work packages to ensure appropriate instrumentation and integration of all COMRADES developments within the evolving scholarly and practitioner communications ecosystem, reporting on these innovations and experiences in the activities in T6.2. WP6 objectives include:

- Establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely internal and external communication;
- Ensure the project achieves widest impact and effective exploitation of results through effective internal and external communications strategy;
- Identify methods and opportunities to ensure sustainability of the COMRADES output beyond the three year duration of the project;
- Communicate project achievements with external stakeholders, and with other CAPS projects in particular;
- Public facing activities including project website, social networks, event coordination.

2 D6.5 Third Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

2.1 Scope of the deliverable

According to the DoA the scope of this deliverable is to provide a full report on the communication and dissemination activities implemented in the second year of the project. In particular, it presents to the reader the dissemination and communication objectives within the period M13-M24 and describes the tools used and activities performed for reaching them.

2.2 Intended audience

The intended audience of this deliverable is described in the table below:

<i>Intended audience</i>	<i>Reasons for interest in reading</i>
COMRADES project partners	To be informed about the dissemination activities during the reporting period.
European Commission	This is a deliverable of the COMRADES project and presents the progress made regarding dissemination and communication of the project in Y3 (<i>report</i>).
Target groups: <i>Activists / deployers, responders, individual citizens, civil society groups, humanitarian organisations and professional networks, scientific community and CAPS network, 11standardization bodies, media, think tanks and other experts</i>	To be informed on the communication and dissemination activities performed within the period M25-M36. Additionally, to be familiarized with the communication tools that were used by WP6 and visit, follow, connect, like, view etc. these tools.
Representatives of organizations involved into similar projects	To share knowledge, information and best practices that can be adopted and utilized in other similar projects.
Anyone interested	To share knowledge, information, lessons learnt during the implementation of the COMRADES project aiming to achieve visibility in wider audiences, raise awareness on the topics of disaster management, volunteerism and in general contributing to the communities' resilience.

Table 1 : Intended audience

2.3 Structure of the document

The D6.5 is comprised of seven chapters and two appendices. The first chapter introduces to the reader the COMRADES project, its objectives as well as a summary of the tasks and the objectives of WP6. The second chapter describes in brief the scope of the current deliverable, the audience that it is addressed to, the methodology followed for its creation and so on. The third one outlines the communication and dissemination objectives for Y3.

The fourth chapter presents the communication tools that the consortium employed and in parallel it delineates all the actions that were undertaken by using these tools within the same period. The fifth chapter gives all the information around the communication and dissemination activities made and highlights (*mostly via respective photos*) some of these activities. Chapter 4 and chapter 5 constitute the main part of the current document.

The sixth one serves as an overview of the reported activities. Lastly, the conclusion summarizes the main points and issues presented in this deliverable.

2.4 Methodology followed

The creation of this deliverable was based on the close collaboration among the consortium for reporting efficiently the performed activities in Y3. Throughout this period each partner informed the WP6 leader for the developments on the topic. Bi-annually, they provided to Gov2u a consolidated report with these activities for ensuring the quality of the provided information. The initial draft version of the D6.5 “Third report on Communication and Dissemination activities” deliverable was produced after collecting all the reports. Later on, it was circulated via email communication to the consortium for reviewing and commenting. After incorporating all comments/suggestions, WP6 leader sent the final version to the project coordinator (OU) for submission to the European Commission.

2.5 Quality of the document

For ensuring the quality of the current document, online communication on the topic via emails and teleconferences was conducted. GOV2U, as WP6 leader, prepared the initial draft and distributed it to project partners for review and contribution. This deliverable uses the official template of the COMRADES project and language quality control has been performed.

2.6 Relation with other WP6 deliverables

This deliverable constitutes an update of the D6.4 “*Second report on Communication and Dissemination activities*” of the current work page. However, it is also interrelated with the other WP6 deliverables. The table below explains the dependencies and relation of each one:

<i>Title of WP6 Deliverable</i>	<i>Dependencies and relation with D6.4</i>
D6.1 “ <i>Dissemination and Communication Action Plan</i> ” {M6}	Set the communication and dissemination strategy, identified groups and envisaged the tools to be used throughout the project’s duration.
D6.2 “ <i>First report on Communication and Dissemination activities</i> ”{M12}	Produced the report for the first year of project’s implementation concerning the dissemination activities that were carried out by the consortium. It also included the progress made related to the action plan and activities that are also described in this deliverable as well.
D6.3 “ <i>Initial exploitation plan</i> ” {M18}	It described the initial plan for the exploitation actions that will follow the upcoming period. Overall, it presented the strategy of the project as a business product and model in the

	<p>relevant market, identifying the needed actions and target audiences to attract. The exploitation actions will be built upon the communication actions (WP6), innovation actions (WP5) and research actions to the extent of community engagement (WP2).</p>
<p>D6.4 <i>“Second report on communication and dissemination activities”</i> {M24}</p>	<p>Produced the annual report for the second year of project’s implementation about the communication and dissemination activities performed within this period. It also included the progress made related to the action plan and activities that are also described in this deliverable as well.</p>
<p>D6.6 <i>“Final exploitation plan”</i> (M36)</p>	<p>It will form an update of the deliverable D6.3 and will describe the final plan for exploiting the project’s outcomes. In other words, it will present the strategy of the project as a business product and model in the relevant market, identifying the needed actions and target audiences to attract. The exploitation actions will be built upon the communication actions (WP6), innovation actions (WP5) and research actions to the extent of community engagement (WP2).</p>

Table 2 : Relation of D6.5 with other WP6 deliverables

3 Communication and Dissemination objectives for Y3

This chapter provides an overview of the dissemination and communication objectives for the second year of project's implementation (*January 2018 – December 2018*).

During this reporting period, WP6 focused its efforts on promoting the project's concept and objectives as well as its first outcomes at local, pan-European and international level. Moreover further expansion of the stakeholders' network and new contacts has been achieved. These activities were realized through various communication channels and dissemination activities.

The main objectives of WP6 for Y2 were the following:

- Maintain and regularly update the COMRADES website;
- Communicate and promote the COMRADES scientific outcomes;
- Expand the stakeholders' network and establish new contacts;
- Exploit the social media accounts and other channels for delivering messages to different audience and engage them;
- Prepare, create, design and deliver the third newsletter issue;
- Participation in events at national, European and international level to raise the awareness and the visibility for the project;
- Organize events such workshops, conferences, lectures etc. for achieving greater engagement with the target groups;
- Establish, maintain and enhance collaboration with other EU funded projects in the same domain, especially with other CAPS projects;
- Investigate ways to exploit the project's results and foster the sustainability of the project after the end of the grant.

The chapters 4 and 5 that follow present in detail how the aforementioned objectives of the project for Y3 were met by the WP6 partners.

4 Communication tools and actions taken

This chapter provides to the reader a detail report about the communication tools that the consortium used during Y3 and in parallel it outlines all the actions that were taken by using these tools within the same period. Chapter 4 together with chapter 5 constitute the main part of the current document.

4.1 COMRADES website

The most important online communication channel, for all kinds of project, is the website. It plays a key role in transmitting the desired messages to target groups and ensures its presence in all available online search engines.

In this context, the COMRADES website was launched in M3 and since then it serves as the major mean of information for communication with the stakeholders. Additions and corrections performed throughout the third year for improving visitor experience of website.

Overall, the project's website has been regularly updated with news and developments around the COMRADES as well as news related to its topic. The content that has been used is easy-to-read in order to ensure that the information it contains can be comprehended by all audiences. This practice assists in growing the number of returning visitors and also attract new ones at the website. The measurement of the performance of the project's website during the reporting period has been made by using the freemium web analytics service named **Google Analytics**. The following table presents the data retrieved from this service and covers the period from 01/01/2018 to 11/12/2018 (*latest measurement*). The respective figures can be found In **Appendix I**.

<i>COMRADES Website Performance in Y3</i>	
Users	1,924
Pageviews	20,960
Sessions	3,181
Number of New Visitors	1,908 (87.3%)
Number of Returning Visitors	278 (12.7%)
Pages / Session	6.59
Avg. Session Duration	00:03:04
Bounce Rate	9.97%

Table 3 : COMRADES Website performance in Y3

The explanation of the terms used for measuring the performance of the COMRADES website is provided below as it has been originally given by the Google Analytics service.

- **Users:** Users who have initiated at least one session during the date range. Learn more about how Analytics calculates the number of users.
- **Pageviews:** Pageviews is the total number of pages viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.

- **Sessions:** Total number of Sessions within the date range. A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with your website, app, etc. All usage data (*Screen Views, Events, Ecommerce, etc.*) is associated with a session.
- **% New Sessions:** An estimate of the percentage of first time visits
- **Avg. Session Duration:** The average length of a Session.
- **Bounce Rate:** The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. A bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds.

Figure 1 : Graphic representation of COMRADES website performance in Y3

Country	Users	% Users
1. France	292	14.97%
2. Greece	276	14.15%
3. United States	201	10.31%
4. United Kingdom	164	8.41%
5. Netherlands	121	6.21%
6. Germany	85	4.36%
7. Italy	80	4.10%
8. Azerbaijan	62	3.18%
9. (not set)	60	3.08%
10. Spain	57	2.92%

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Figure 2 : Top 10 countries - Demographics of COMRADES website in Y3

As this deliverable the final report of our project the table below presents an overview of the project’s website performance throughout its lifecycle. We have divided the metrics in three categories i.e. one per year of COMRADES implementation. The **first year (Y1)** is the initial measurement while **year 2 (Y2)** is the interim and **the year 3 (Y3)** the final one.

Overview of COMRADES Website Performance (Jan. '16 – Dec. '18)		
Users	Number of Users in Y1 (Initial measurement)	1,179
	Number of Users in Y2 (interim measurement)	1,482

	Number of Users in Y3 <i>(final measurement)</i>	1,924
Pageviews	Number of Pageviews in Y1 <i>(Initial measurement)</i>	11,594
	Number of Pageviews in Y2 <i>(interim measurement)</i>	17,443
	Number of Pageviews in Y3 <i>(final measurement)</i>	20,960
Sessions	Number of Sessions in Y1 <i>(Initial measurement)</i>	1,970
	Number of Sessions in Y2 <i>(interim measurement)</i>	2,337
	Number of Sessions in Y3 <i>(final measurement)</i>	3,181
Number of New Visitors	Number of New visitors in Y1 <i>(Initial measurement)</i>	326 (86.7)
	Number of New Visitors in Y2 <i>(interim measurement)</i>	873 (37.4%)
	Number of New Visitors in Y3 <i>(final measurement)</i>	1,908 (87.3%)
Number of Returning Visitors	Number of Returning Visitors in Y1 <i>(Initial measurement)</i>	50 (13.3%)
	Number of Returning Visitors in Y2 <i>(interim measurement)</i>	1,464 (62.6%)
	Number of Returning Visitors in Y3 <i>(final measurement)</i>	278 (12.7%)
Pages / Session	Pages / Session in Y1 <i>(Initial measurement)</i>	5.89
	Pages / Session in Y2 <i>(interim measurement)</i>	7.46
	Pages / Session in Y3 <i>(final measurement)</i>	6.59
Avg. Session Duration	Avg. Session Duration in Y1 <i>(Initial measurement)</i>	00:03:51

	Avg. Session Duration in Y2 (interim measurement)	00:03:19
	Avg. Session Duration in Y3 (final measurement)	00:03:04
Bounce Rate	Bounce Rate in Y1 (Initial measurement)	21.68%
	Bounce Rate in Y2 (interim measurement)	4.28%
	Bounce Rate in Y3 (final measurement)	9.97%

Table 4 : Overview of COMRADES website performance (Jan. '16 – Dec. '18)

Country	Users	% Users
1. United States	615	15.98%
2. Greece	449	11.67%
3. United Kingdom	416	10.81%
4. France	330	8.57%
5. Netherlands	222	5.77%
6. Italy	170	4.42%
7. Germany	135	3.51%
8. (not set)	115	2.99%
9. Spain	114	2.96%
10. Azerbaijan	99	2.57%

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Figure 3 : Top 10 countries - Demographics of COMRADES website Jan. '16 – Dec. '18

4.2 Newsletter

The newsletter is a communication tool that assists WP6 in reaching the target groups and conveying to them the major COMRADES developments with main aim to attract their attention and engage them. The newsletter issues are delivered via email (*e-newsletter*) and for this reason they are published corresponding to the internal activity frequency of the project, in order to avoid spamming target audiences with little content. For distributing (*via email*) the e-newsletter issues we use the free service of [Moosend](#). It is an email marketing service provider where its users can manage their mailing lists, craft their newsletters, schedule their delivery and track and evaluate their performance.

The period that we examine (*January 2018 – December 2018*) our project published one newsletter issue, which constitutes the third newsletter issue from the beginning of its lifetime. The latest issue was published in March 2018 and as a main topic had the deployment of the COMRADES platform during the general election in Kenya. Particularly, the third newsletter had two “versions” with almost the same articles. One version was more focused on the role that COMRADES platform played in monitoring the Kenyan Elections and the other one the technical evaluation of the platform after using the COMRADES platform in Kenyan elections.

Figure 4 : Third Newsletter Issue (Mar.'18)

4.3 Press Release

The press release constitutes one of the most popular tools for communicating project’s major developments and news. In our case we use it for announcing the deployment of Ushahidi COMRADES in order to monitor the Kenyan general elections. It is available online at project’s website in “Press Kit” section, “Press Releases” subsection.

Figure 5 : Press Release – Kenyan Elections

4.4 COMRADES social media

Social media are powerful and significant tools for communication with a wider audience as through one source many recipients can be reached. For greater outreach and also taking advantage of the benefits that these means offer, accounts in Twitter, LinkedIn and a Facebook page were created from the very start of the project. During Y3 we created also Google+ profile in order to make COMRADES presence known in this social media network.

4.4.1 Facebook page

Facebook is an online social media and social networking service. After registering to use the site, users can create a user profile indicating their name, occupation, schools attended and so on. Users can add other users as "friends", exchange messages, post status updates and digital photos, share digital videos and links, use various software applications ("*apps*"), and receive notifications when others update their profiles or make posts.

The Facebook page of the COMRADES project was created in January 2016 (*M1*) and since then it has been regularly updated with project news, interesting events and relevant information such as news from the CAPs projects. According to the **interim measurement** on 4th December 2017 the number of page likes was 138. In comparison with the **initial measurement** in December 2016 the number of page likes has been increased in 272.97% or 101 new likes in Y2. In the **final measurement** dated on the 11th of December 2018 the page likes were 172 which means **24.64% increase** in Y3 or 34 new page likes during the reporting period.

Figure 6 : COMRADES Facebook Page

<i>Facebook Page</i>	
Created in <i>(Project Month)</i>	January 2016 <i>(M1)</i>
URL	https://www.facebook.com/comradesproject/
Mention	@comradesproject
Number of Page Likes Y1 <i>(Initial Measurement)</i>	37 Likes <i>(December 2016)</i>
Number of Page Likes Y2 <i>(Interim Measurement)</i>	138 Likes <i>(December 2017)</i>
Number of Page Likes Y3 <i>(Final Measurement)</i>	172 Likes <i>(December 2018)</i>
% Likes <i>increase / decrease in Y3</i> <i>($\frac{{Y3-Y2}}{Y2} \times 100$)</i>	24.64 % increase in Y3

Table 5 : Facebook Page Performance

Figure 7 : Page Likes Growth – Facebook Page

4.4.2 Twitter profile

Twitter is an online news and social networking service where users post and interact with messages, "tweets", restricted to 140 characters. Registered users can post tweets, but those who are unregistered can only read them.

Figure 8 : COMRADES Twitter profile

The Twitter profile of the COMRADES project was created in January 2016 (M1) and since then it has been regularly updated with project news, interesting events and relevant information such as news from the CAPs projects. According to the **interim measurement** on the 4th December 2017 the number of followers was 309. Compared with the **initial measurement** in December 2016 the number of followers were increased in 41.09% or 90 new followers in Y2. The **final measurement** dated on the 11th of December 2018 showed that in Y3 there was an **increase of 30.75% (compared to Y2)** in twitter followers or 95 new followers during the reporting period.

Twitter Profile	
Created in (Project Month)	January 2016 (M1)
URL	https://twitter.com/comradesproject
Mention	@comradesproject
Number of Followers Y1 (Initial Measurement)	219 Followers (December 2016)
Number of Followers Y2 (Interim Measurement)	309 Followers (December 2017)
Number of Followers Y3 (Final Measurement)	404 Followers (December 2018)
% Followers increase / decrease in Y3 ($\{Y3-Y2\}/Y2 \times 100$)	30.75 % increase in Y3

Table 6 : Twitter profile Performance

Figure 9 : Followers growth - Twitter

Figure 10 : Tweet impressions in Y3 – Twitter

Figure 11 : Profile visits in Y3 – Twitter

4.4.3 LinkedIn profile

LinkedIn is a business-and employment-oriented social networking service that operates via websites and mobile apps. It is mainly used for professional networking, including employers posting jobs and job seekers posting their CVs. LinkedIn allows members (*both workers and employers*) to create profiles and "connections" to each other in an online social network which may represent real-world professional relationships. Members can invite anyone (*whether an existing member or not*) to become a connection. The "gated-access approach" (*where contact with any professional requires either an existing relationship or an introduction through a contact of theirs*) is intended to build trust among the service's members.

Figure 12 : COMRADES LinkedIn profile

The LinkedIn profile of the COMRADES project was created in January 2016 (M1) and since then it has been regularly updated with project news, interesting events and relevant information such as news from the CAPs projects.

According to the **interim measurement** on the 4th December 2017 the number of connections was 123. Compared with the **initial measurement** in December 2016 the number of followers were increased in 80.88% or 55 new connections in Y2. The **final measurement** dated on the 11th of December 2018 showed that in Y3 there was an **increase of 34.96%** (compared to Y2) in LinkedIn connections or 43 new followers during the reporting period.

<i>LinkedIn Profile</i>	
Created in <i>(Project Month)</i>	January 2016 <i>(M1)</i>
URL	https://www.linkedin.com/in/comradesproject/
Number of Connections Y1 <i>(Initial Measurement)</i>	68 Connections <i>(December 2016)</i>
Number of Connections Y2 <i>(Interim Measurement)</i>	123 Connections <i>(December 2017)</i>
Number of Connections Y3 <i>(Final Measurement)</i>	166 Connections <i>(December 2018)</i>
% Connections <i>increase / decrease in Y3</i> <i>{(Y3-Y2)/Y2 x 100}</i>	34.96 % increase in Y3

Table 7 : Current status of the LinkedIn profile

Figure 13 : Connections growth – LinkedIn

4.4.4 Google+ profile

Google+ is an Internet-based social network that is owned and operated by Google. In Y3 we created a profile in order to have COMRADES presence in this social media network for maximizing its visibility. It was regularly updated with similar posts that we used in the rest of social media account of the project. However it was not feasible to gain followers (*only one follower*) despite our communication's team attempts. This social network is not popular among social network users (*low user engagement*) and due to this fact Google plans to cease its operation (*consumer version*) in April 2019.

Figure 14 : COMRADES Google+ profile

4.5 Digital Publishing Platforms

Electronic publishing (also referred to as *e-publishing* or *digital publishing* or *online publishing*) includes the digital publication of e-books, digital magazines, and the development of digital libraries and catalogues.

In COMRADES we have used three different platforms (*Issuu, Scribd, LinkedIn Slideshare*) for digital publishing that served as tools of dissemination for promoting the outcomes of the project such as public deliverables (*approved by EC*), papers (*publications*) and promotional materials (*e.g. poster, newsletter issues, etc.*). Although, they were not foreseen in the DoA we decided to use these tools under the general frame of communicating the project's result via all known available solutions that would assist in further disseminating the COMRADES to a wider audience.

4.5.1 Issuu profile

Issuu is a free electronic publishing platform for magazines, catalogs, and newspapers. We created the COMRADES profile on Issuu in June 2017 (*M18*) and we continued deploying the platform during Y3. The platform does not provide any more free statistics about the

performance of the profile and the published items. However information can be retrieved for free about its overall performance.

<i>Issuu Profile</i>		
Created in (Project Month)	June 2017 (M18)	
URL	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject	
Reads	Reads in Y2	66
	Reads in Y3	47
	Total Reads (Y2+Y3)	113
Impressions	Impressions in Y2	462
	Impressions in Y3	1,255
	Total Impressions (Y2+Y3)	1,717
Shares	Shares in Y2	1
	Shares in Y3	4
	Total Shares (Y2+Y3)	5
Published items	Published items in Y2	22
	Published items in Y3	6
	Total Published items (Y2+Y3)	28

Table 8 : Overview of the Issuu Profile

Statistics for **COMRADES EU Project**

You have been a member since June 23rd 2017

113 Reads	1,717 Impressions	0 Followers
0 Likes	5 Shares	0 Link-outs

Figure 15 : COMRADES Issuu profile overall performance

The explanation of the metrics terms (as given by Issuu) that are showcased in **Figure 21** is:

- **Reads:** Counted each time a user opened a publication for more than 2 seconds.
- **Impressions:** Counted each time a publication was displayed to a user in an embedded or on Issuu.
- **Followers:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Likes:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Shares:** The number of times a user shared your publication from Issuu.
- **Link-outs:** Number of clicks on a publisher made link.
- **Average time spent:** The average time readers spent reading this publication
- **Read time:** The total time readers spend reading this publication

Figure 16 : COMRADES Issuu profile

Table 9 lists all published items on COMRADES Issuu profile during Y3.

No.	Title of published item	URL	Type
1.	1st Press Release: Ushahidi COMRADES platform monitors the Kenyan Elections	https://issuu.com/home/published/uchaguzi-press-release_feb2018	Press Release
2.	Classifying Crises-Information Relevancy with Semantics	https://issuu.com/home/published/eswc2018_paper_76	Paper
3.	An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	https://issuu.com/comradesuproject/docs/ranlp006	Paper

4.	Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack	https://issuu.com/home/published/helping_crisis_responders_find_the	Paper
5.	Evaluating Platforms for Community Sensemaking: Using the Case of the Kenyan Elections	https://issuu.com/home/published/evaluatingplatformsforcommunity_sens	Paper
6.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet - Updated	https://issuu.com/home/published/comrades_factsheet-webv	Promotional material

Table 9 : Published items on Issuu in Y3

4.5.2 Scribd profile

Scribd is a digital library, e-book and audiobook subscription service. The profile of COMRADES on SCRIBD was created in June 2017 (M18) and we continued deploying the platform during Y3.

Scribd Profile		
Created in (Project Month)	June 2017 (M18)	
URL	https://www.scribd.com/user/362001050/COMRADES-EU-Project	
Views	Views in Y2	88
	Views in Y3	53
	Total Views (Y2+Y3)	141
Published items	Published items in Y2	22
	Published items in Y3	3
	Total Published items (Y2+Y3)	25

Table 10 : Overview of Scribd Profile

The following table lists all published items on COMRADES Scribd profile in Y3.

No.	Title of published item	URL	Type
1.	Classifying Crises-Information Relevancy with Semantics	https://www.scribd.com/document/382182908/Classifying-Crises-Information-Relevancy-with-Semantics	Paper

2.	An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	https://www.scribd.com/document/382183313/An-Extensible-Multilingual-Open-Source-Lemmatizer	Paper
3.	Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack	https://www.scribd.com/document/382183972/Helping-Crisis-Responders-Find-the-Informative-Needle-in-the-Tweet-Haystack	Paper

Table 11 : Published items on Scribd Profile in Y3

We have uploaded 25 items (*deliverables, papers, promotional materials*) in total that are freely accessible and downloadable. **Table 12** lists all published items in the profile and provides their metrics (*views*).

No.	Title of published item	URL	Total Views
1	Sustainable Performance Measurement for Humanitarian Supply Chain Operations	https://www.scribd.com/document/365373421/Sustainable-Performance-Measurement-for-Humanitarian-Supply-Chain-Operations	15
2	An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	https://www.scribd.com/document/382183313/An-Extensible-Multilingual-Open-Source-Lemmatizer	10
3	SemEval-2017 Task 8: RumourEval: Determining rumour veracity and support for rumours	https://www.scribd.com/document/365375332/SemEval-2017-Task-8-RumourEval-Determining-rumour-veracity-and-support-for-rumours	9
4	Detecting Important Life Events on Twitter Using Frequent Semantic and Syntactic Subgraphs	https://www.scribd.com/document/365370531/Detecting-Important-Life-Events-on-Twitter-Using-Frequent-Semantic-and-Syntactic-Subgraphs	8
5	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	https://www.scribd.com/document/365292235/D6-1-Dissemination-and-Communication-Action-Plan	8
6	COMRADES EU Project Poster	https://www.scribd.com/document/365178086/COMRADES-EU-Project-Poster	8
7	Classifying Crises-Information Relevancy with Semantics	https://www.scribd.com/document/382182908/Classifying-Crises-Information-Relevancy-with-Semantics	7
8	D3.1 Multilingual content processing methods	https://www.scribd.com/document/365289774/D3-1-Multilingual-content-processing-methods	6

D6.5 Third Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

9	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.2 - June 2017	https://www.scribd.com/document/365190353/comrades-eu-project-newsletter-issue-no-2-june-2017	6
10	Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack	https://www.scribd.com/document/382183972/Helping-Crisis-Responders-Find-the-Informative-Needle-in-the-Tweet-Haystack	5
11	Prospecting Socially-Aware Concepts and Artefacts for Designing for Community Resilience	https://www.scribd.com/document/365375000/Prospecting-Socially-Aware-Concepts-and-Artefacts-for-Designing-for-Community-Resilience	5
12	On Semantics and Deep Learning for Event Detection in Crisis Situations	https://www.scribd.com/document/365374554/On-Semantics-and-Deep-Learning-for-Event-Detection-in-Crisis-Situations	5
13	Behind the Scenes of Scenario-Based Training: Understanding Scenario Design and Requirements in High-Risk and Uncertain Environments	https://www.scribd.com/document/365374043/Behind-the-Scenes-of-Scenario-Based-Training-Understanding-Scenario-Design-and-Requirements-in-High-Risk-and-Uncertain-Environments	5
14	COMRADES EU Project Brochure	https://www.scribd.com/document/352069254/COMRADES-EU-Project-Brochure	5
15	COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	https://www.scribd.com/document/352069105/COMRADES-EU-Project-Overall-Presentation	5
16	A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media	https://www.scribd.com/document/365374244/A-Semantic-Graph-based-Approach-for-Radicalisation-Detection-on-Social-Media	4
17	DoRES — A Three-tier Ontology for Modelling Crises in the Digital Age	https://www.scribd.com/document/365364886/DoRES-A-Three-tier-Ontology-for-Modelling-Crises-in-the-Digital-Age	4
18	D2.2 Socio-Technical Community Requirements	https://www.scribd.com/document/365289138/D2-2-Socio-Technical-Community-Requirements	4
19	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.1 - July 2016	https://www.scribd.com/document/365190198/comrades-eu-project-newsletter-issue-no-1-july-2016	4
20	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://www.scribd.com/document/352068989/COMRADES-EU-Project-Factsheet	4

21	Designing for Networked Community Resilience	https://www.scribd.com/document/365376636/Designing-for-Networked-Community-Resilience	3
22	D4.1 Enriched Semantic Models of Emergency Events	https://www.scribd.com/document/365291945/d4-1-enriched-semantic-models-of-emergency-events	3
23	D2.3 Community Based Evaluation	https://www.scribd.com/document/365288905/d2-3-community-based-evaluation	3
24	D2.1 Requirements for boosting community resilience in crisis situation	https://www.scribd.com/document/365285824/D2-1-Requirements-for-boosting-community-resilience-in-crisis-situation	3
25	D6.2 First report on Communication and Dissemination activities	https://www.scribd.com/document/365292391/D6-2-First-report-on-Communication-and-Dissemination-activities	2

Table 12 : List of published items & metrics – Scribd profile

4.5.3 LinkedIn SlideShare account

LinkedIn SlideShare is a slide hosting service where users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. It also provides to the users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content.

<i>LinkedIn SlideShare Profile</i>		
Created in (Project Month)	June 2017 (M18)	
URL	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject	
Views	Views in Y2	361
	Views in Y3	599
	Total Views (Y2+Y3)	960
Published items	Published items in Y2	20
	Published items in Y3	5
	Total Published items (Y2+Y3)	25

Table 13 : Overview of LinkedIn SlideShare profile

No.	Title of published item	URL	Type
1.	Evaluating Platforms for Community Sensemaking: Using the Case of the Kenyan Elections	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/evaluating-platforms-for-community-sensemaking-using-the-case-of-the-kenyan-elections	Paper
2.	Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/helping-crisis-responders-find-the-informative-needle-in-the-tweet-haystack	Paper
3.	An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/an-extensible-multilingual-open-source-lemmatizer	Paper
4.	Classifying Crises-Information Relevancy with Semantics	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/classifying-crisisinformation-relevancy-with-semantics	Paper
5.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-factsheet-102768206	Promotional Material

Table 14 : Published items on LinkedIn SlideShare account in Y

The service of analytics for COMRADES account is provided free of charge by the LinkedIn Slideshare and we have included all the available information in the current report. The analytics are represented in figures 17, 18, 19 and 20.

Figure 17 : Views summary in Y3 - LinkedIn SlideShare account

Top content

Name	Views
COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	159
Sustainable Performance Measurement for Humanitarian Supply Chain Operations	57
D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	43
An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	36
COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	21

Figure 18 : Top content - LinkedIn SlideShare account

Top countries

Name	Views
Greece	169
United States	87
France	36
Germany	31
Ukraine	14

Figure 19 : Top countries - LinkedIn SlideShare account

Figure 20 : Traffic sources - LinkedIn SlideShare account

Figure 21 : COMRADES LinkedIn SlideShare account

The following table presents all published items as well as analytics (total views).

No.	Title of published item	URL	Type	Total Views
1.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-factsheet-102768206	Promotional Material	28
2.	Evaluating Platforms for Community Sensemaking: Using the Case of the Kenyan Elections	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/evaluating-platforms-for-community-sensemaking-using-the-case-of-the-kenyan-elections	Paper	23
3.	Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/helping-crisis-responders-find-the-informative-needle-in-the-tweet-haystack	Paper	21
4.	An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/an-extensible-multilingual-open-source-lemmatizer	Paper	36
5.	Classifying Crises-Information Relevancy with Semantics	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/classify	Paper	11

		ng-crisisinformation-relevancy-with-semantics		
6.	D6.2 First report on Communication and Dissemination activities	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d62-first-report-on-communication-and-dissemination-activities	Public deliverable	35
7.	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d61-dissemination-and-communication-action-plan	Public deliverable	110
8.	D3.1 Multilingual content processing methods	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d31-multilingual-content-processing-methods	Public deliverable	27
9.	D4.1 Enriched Semantic Models of Emergency Events	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d41-enriched-semantic-models-of-emergency-events	Public deliverable	30
10.	Designing for Networked Community Resilience	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/designing-for-networked-community-resilience-82655928	Paper	21
11.	SemEval-2017 Task 8: RumourEval: Determining rumour veracity and support for rumours	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/semEval2017-task-8-rumoureval-determining-rumour-veracity-and-support-for-rumours	Paper	24
12.	Prospecting Socially-Aware Concepts and Artefacts for Designing for Community Resilience	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/prospecting-socially-aware-concepts-and-artefacts-for-designing-for-community-resilience	Paper	18
13.	On Semantics and Deep Learning for Event Detection in Crisis Situations	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/on-semantics-and-deep-learning-for-event-detection-in-crisis-situations	Paper	38
14.	A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/a-semantic-graphbased-approach-for-radicalisation-	Paper	44

		detection-on-social-media-82654394		
15.	Behind the Scenes of Scenario-Based Training: Understanding Scenario Design and Requirements in High-Risk and Uncertain Environments	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/behind-the-scenes-of-scenariobased-training-understanding-scenario-design-and-requirements-in-highrisk-and-uncertain-environments	Paper	29
16.	Sustainable Performance Measurement for Humanitarian Supply Chain Operations	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/sustainable-performance-measurement-for-humanitarian-supply-chain-operations	Paper	65
17.	Detecting Important Life Events on Twitter Using Frequent Semantic and Syntactic Subgraphs	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/detecting-important-life-events-on-twitter-using-frequent-semantic-and-syntactic-subgraphs	Paper	45
18	DoRES — A Three-tier Ontology for Modelling Crises in the Digital Age	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/dores-a-threetier-ontology-for-modelling-crises-in-the-digital-age-82646499	Paper	20
19.	D2.1 Requirements for boosting community resilience in crisis situation	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d21-requirements-for-boosting-community-resilience-in-crisis-situation	Public deliverable	26
20.	COMRADES EU Project Poster	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-poster	Promotional Material	14
21.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-factsheet	Promotional Material	15
22.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.1 - July 2016	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-newsletter-issue-no1-july-2016	Newsletter Issue	41
23.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.2 - June 2017	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-newsletter-issue-no2-june-2017	Newsletter Issue	31

24.	COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-overall-presentation	Presentation	182
25.	COMRADES EU Project Brochure	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-brochure	Promotional Material	26

Table 15 : List of Slideshare items & metrics

4.6 Promotional Materials

In Y3, we created mementos that were given to participants of ICT 2018 event who visited our project’s booth. These promotional materials were stickers, USB sticks and key rings with the COMRADES logo on. Additionally, a special large poster was created for the needs of this event.

Figure 22 : COMRADES mementos for ICT 2018 event

Figure 23 : COMRADES poster for ICT 2018 event

4.7 YouTube Channel

In the very early days of July 2018 we created the COMRADES YouTube channel in order to better communicate our project and its videos that include the tools of the project as well as its outcomes. It assisted the communication activities as a marketing tool. In total we created four videos and uploaded at the channel.

Figure 24 : COMRADES YouTube channel

YouTube channel	
Created in (Project Month)	June 2018 (M18)
URL	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCMLRUU7gzhoRyp6A9Z46zIQ
Total Views	182
Published items	4
Subscribers	2
Subscriptions	8

Table 16 : Overview of YouTube channel

No.	Video Title	URL	Total Views
1.	ΠΛΑΤΦΟΡΜΑ COMRADES Action24 - Today - Μάρα Μπάρμπα - 28/06/18	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8iOjlgNe_6I	112
2.	COMRADES Humanitarian ChatBot	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRugR_7wGOM	40
3.	Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES) - COMRADES EU Project	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aCDK5GnI0_Q	19

4.	CREES API as Google Sheets Add-on - Tutorial Video - COMRADES EU Project	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eolrQPuaW6k	11
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Table 17 : List of uploaded videos on YouTube channel

5 Communication and Dissemination Activities

The current chapter includes all the information around the communication and dissemination activities performed in Y2. For readers ease, this information is presented via tables. Chapter 5 together with chapter 4 constitutes the main part of the current document.

5.1 Organization of events

In 5.1 the reader can find in detail all the events that were organized by the COMRADES consortium during the reporting period. These events had major contribution in the offline dissemination of the project due to the fact that they attracted attention and expanded its network in stakeholders, citizens, media, policy makers etc. and also provided valuable feedback to the project for its upcoming activities in Y3.

5.1.1 List of the COMRADES events

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Partner</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event</i>	<i>Description of the event</i>
1.	TUD	Workshop University of Indonesia	Nov 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia	40, students + lecturers
2.	TUD	Workshop UN Global Pulse	Nov 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia	15, UN Global Pulse Staff
3.	TUD	Youth in Science Engineering, Technology and Innovation for DRR conference	Nov 2018	Serpoong, Indonesia	80, Academia, students
4.	TUD	Avans Hogescholen	Oct 2018	Den Bosch, Netherlands	30 students + lecturers
5.	TUD	Delft Global Event	Oct 2018	Delft, Netherlands	20 general public
6.	OU	Social Media Analysis for Situation Awareness during Crises	April 2018	Lyon, France	15 researchers and practitioners
7.	TUD	Workshop Campus Vesta	March 2018	Ranst, Belgium	30 professional crisis responders
8.	USFD	RumourEval 2019: Evaluation Competition and Workshop	August 2018 - Jan 2019 (evaluation);	Minneapolis, US	176 participants registered for competition.

			June 6-7 2019 Workshop		15-30 expected at workshop. Academics/res earchers
9.	OU	STEM Lecturer at Denbigh School	November 14	Milton Keynes, UK	70 people, students and staff

Table 18 : List of the COMRADES events

5.1.2 Highlights from the COMRADES events

Figure 25 : Workshop with UN Global Pulse, Jakarta (Indonesia)

Figure 26 : Workshop at the University of Indonesia in Jakarta

Figure 27 : Youth in Science Engineering, Technology and Innovation for DRR conference (Serpoong, Indonesia)

5.2 Participation in third party events

5.2.1 List of the COMRADES participation in third party events

No.	Partner	Name of the event	Date of the event	Location of the event	Description of the event
1.	Gov2u	DigiNET Training Week	28 August - 1 September 2018	Athens, Greece	Training week organized by DigiNET project (Erasmus+) and addressed to youth and potential entrepreneurs who wish to create their own e-enterprise and come from Spain, Malta, Greece, Bulgaria and UK.
2.	TUD	ISCRAM	May 2018	Rochester, USA	Academia
3.	TUD	ISD 2018 (Information Systems Development)	August 2018	Lund, Sweden	Academia
4.	TUD	GFP (Global Flood Partnerships)	June 2018	Delft, Netherlands	Academia

5.	TUD	PSCE	Dec 2018	Bled, Slovenia	Practitioners
6	OU	ICT2018	Dec 2018	Vienna, Austria	>5000 Practitioners, Academia
7.	OU	Nesta workshop on “Tech for everyone, by everyone: citizen-centred digital innovation for good”	Dec 2018	Vienna, Austria	25 from research and industry
8.	OU	Int. Conf. Social Informatics (SocInfo)	Sept 2018	St Petersburg, Russia	Academia (~150)
9.	TUD	HumTechLab Showcase	October 2018	Delft, The Netherlands	30 students and researchers
10.	TUD	PSC-Europe Conference	December 2018	Bled, Slovenia	40 academics and practitioners

Table 19 : List of the COMRADES participation in third party events

5.2.2 Highlights from the COMRADES participation in third party events

5.2.2.1 COMRADES at the DigiNET training week

The [DigiNet project](#) funded under the Erasmus+ programme organized the **DigiNet Training Week** which took place in Athens, Greece from the 28th of August until 1st of September 2018.

The communication team of our project, **Vassiliki Zalavra** (*Gov2u*) and **Pantelis Kanellopoulos** (*Gov2u*) were invited by [Electronic Compass](#) as guest speakers to the training and they presented to the audience how to build and implement a successful social media strategy.

Within this context, Vassiliki and Pantelis primarily presented the COMRADES project and later on the strategy that they follow in order to promote the project and its results. In particular, they talked about creating effective messages and the social media networks that they deploy as well as the lesson learnt through their experience on the topic.

The audience of the training consisted of youth and potential entrepreneurs who wish to create their own e-enterprise and come from Spain, Malta, Greece, Bulgaria and UK.

Figure 28 : COMRADES presented at the DigiNet training week

5.2.2.2 COMRADES awarded at ICISO 2018

Our partners Lara Picolo (*Open University, UK*), Kenny Meesters (*Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands*) and Shadrock Roberts (*Ushahidi, Kenya*) won the award of the best presentation at the 18th International Conference of Informatics and Semiotics in Organizations (*ICISO 2018*) for the COMRADES presentation: “Building a socio-technical perspective of community resilience with semiotic approach”.

Figure 29 : COMRADES awarded at ICISO 2018

5.2.2.3 COMRADES paper presentation at the 15th ISCRAM Conference

Our partners Vittorio Nespeca, Kenny Meesters and Tina Comes from the Delft University of Technology, presented the paper “Evaluating Platforms for Community Sense making: Using

the Case of the Kenyan Elections” at the 15th ISCRAM Conference. The conference was held at the Rochester Institute of Technology in NY, USA from 20th to 23rd of May 2018.

The research presented in this paper focuses on studying the sense making process of non-mandated responders through the aid of IT platforms such as the COMRADES platform. Using a comprehensive evaluation exercise based on real data from the 2017 Kenyan elections, the authors examine the development of a shared situational awareness, the related workflows and the use of this awareness in a group decision making process. In this manner, the requirements for resilience platforms as well as further research directions are identified.

Figure 30 : COMRADES paper presentation at the 15th ISCRAM Conference

5.2.2.4 COMRADES presented at the ICT2018 event

COMRADES team organised a 3 day exhibition at ICT 2018 in Vienna, to showcase the various technologies developed in H2020 COMRADES project. More than 5000 people attended the event this year, so the COMRADES booth was super busy! Visitors to the booth were able to see and use a crisis mapping platform that was powered with AI technologies to automatically filter, categorise, and verify crisis information shared on Twitter.

Prof. Alani also presented COMRADES at a session organised by Nesta on "Tech for everyone, by everyone: citizen-centred digital innovation for good". The presentation showed the innovation of COMRADES which brought the latest AI techniques to the field of crisis information processing and management.

Figure 31 : COMRADES booth at the ICT 2018

Figure 32 : COMRADES presentation at the ICT 2018 during the session “Tech for everyone by everyone”

Figure 33 : Poster of the “Tech for everyone, by everyone” session

5.2.2.5 COMRADES paper presentation at the ISWC 2018

Our partners from the Open University presented the paper “Cross Lingual Classification of Crisis Data” at the ISWC 2018.

Figure 34 : COMRADES paper presentation at the ISWC 2018

5.2.2.6 COMRADES presented at the ECCE 2019

Our partners from the Open University presented COMRADES at the ECCE 2019. Ms. Lara Piccolo talked in the chatbot session about our project’s paper “Designing ChatBots for Crises: Contrasting Potential and Reality”.

Figure 35 : Ms. Lara Piccolo from OU at the ECCE 2019 talking in chatbot session

5.2.2.7 Sharing COMRADES results at the HCI 2018

Our partners from the Open University participated at the HCI 2018 and had the opportunity to share COMRADES results.

Figure 36 : Sharing COMRADES results at the HCI 2018

5.3 Collaboration with other projects & initiatives

In Y3 the project focused on promoting and sharing its results to stakeholders and general public. In this context for enhancing the dissemination activities of the project we contacted, invited and established collaborations with other EU funded projects and initiatives.

5.3.1 List of the established collaborations

No	Partner	Project's Name	Contact organization	Date	Description (collaboration activity)
1.	Gov2u	Families_Share (CAPS Project) Website: www.families-share.eu	Vilabs Website: https://vilabs.eu/	9 Nov. 2018	Communication liaison (cross dissemination synergy)
2.	Gov2u	Plastic Twist (CAPS Project) Website: https://ptwist.eu/	Artistotle University of Thessaloniki (School of Informatics) Website: www.csd.auth.gr	19 Jul. 2018	Communication liaison (cross dissemination synergy)
3.	Gov2u	FLOOD-serv Website: www.floodserv-project.eu	SIVECO Website: www.siveco.ro	25 Jul. 2018	Communication liaison (cross dissemination synergy)
4.	Gov2u	CROWD4ROADS (CAPS Project) Website: www.c4rs.eu	Università degli Studi di Urbino Carlo Bo Website: www.uniurb.it	19 Jul. 2018	Communication liaison (cross dissemination synergy)
5.	Gov2u	IREACT Website: www.i-react.eu	scienseed Website: http://scienseed.com/	14 Oct. 2018	Communication liaison (cross dissemination synergy)
6.	TUD	e2mc Website: www.e2mc-project.eu	TUD / Vesta Website: www.campusvesta.be	Dec. 2018	Joint workshop at PSCE conference
7.	OU	DARWIN Website:	SINTEF Website:	Dec. 2018	Info exchange on crisis info processing and

		https://h2020darwin.eu/	www.sintef.no		related challenges
8.	OU	InVID Website: www.invid-project.eu	MODUL Technology Website: www.modultech.eu	Dec. 2018	Collaboration agreement on info validity assessment

Table 20 : List of established collaborations with other projects & initiatives

5.3.1.1 CAPS projects (short description)

Throughout Y3, the communication team of COMRADES continued contacting via email CAPS projects with main aim to establish communication liaisons for further promotion of the project expanding its network. The descriptions of the CAPS projects that responded to our invitations are provided at the table below.

No.	CAPS project	Description	URL
1.	Families-Share	Funded under the Information and Communication Technologies programme of Horizon 2020's the Families_Share project is developing a social networking and awareness-raising platform dedicated to encouraging childcare and work/life balance. The platform capitalises on neighborhood networks and enables citizens to come together to share tasks, time and skills relevant to childcare and after-school education/leisure, where these have become unaffordable in times of stagnation and austerity.	www.families-share.eu
2.	Plastic Twist	PTwist aims to design, deploy, and validate an open platform which will twist plastic reuse practices, by boosting citizens' awareness, circular economy practices, and sustainable innovation in line with the new plastics economy vision.	https://ptwist.eu/
3.	CROWD4ROADS	The CROWD4ROADS project combines trip sharing and crowd sensing initiatives to harness collective intelligence to contribute to the solution of the sustainability issues of road passenger transport, by increasing the car occupancy rate and by engaging drivers and passengers in road monitoring.	www.c4rs.eu

Table 21 : Description of CAPS projects that collaborated with COMRADES in Y3

5.3.1.2 Other EU funded projects (short description)

Beyond of establishing synergies with CAPS projects, we also focused on other EU funded projects (under Horizon 2020 programme action) related to COMRADES topic which led in

interesting discussions on further collaborations about their outcomes. The descriptions of these projects are provided at the table below.

<i>No.</i>	<i>EU funded project</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>URL</i>
1.	FLOOD-serv	The overall objective of FLOOD-serv is to develop and to provide a pro-active and personalised citizen-centric public service application that will enhance the involvement of the citizen and will harness the collaborative power of ICT networks (networks of people, of knowledge, of sensors) to raise awareness on flood risks and to enable collective risk mitigation solutions and response actions.	www.floodserv-project.eu
2.	IREACT	Due to climate change, floods, wildfires and other extreme weather events are becoming more frequent and intense. This scenario poses a challenge for current risk management systems. I-REACT aims to develop a solution through the integration and modelling of data coming multiple sources.	www.i-react.eu
3.	e2mc	E2mC aims at demonstrating the technical and operational feasibility of the integration of social media analysis and crowdsourced information within both the Mapping and Early Warning Components of Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS). The Project will develop a prototype of a new EMS Service Component (Copernicus Witness), designed to exploit social media analysis and crowdsourcing capabilities to generate a new Product of the EMS Portfolio.	www.e2mc-project.eu
4.	DARWIN	The project is focused on improving responses to expected and unexpected crises affecting critical societal structures during natural disasters (<i>e.g. flooding, earthquakes</i>) and man-made disasters (<i>e.g. cyber-attacks</i>). To achieve this, DARWIN will develop European resilience management guidelines aimed at critical infrastructure managers, crisis and emergency response managers, service providers, first responders and policy makers. Infrastructure operators will have up-to-date and effective guidelines at their disposal to facilitate faster, more effective and highly adaptive responses to crises. This will have a direct impact on the safety of European citizens	https://h2020darwin.eu/

		in times of crisis and disaster into the future. The DARWIN resilience guidelines will also be of significant benefit for governments of EU member states.	
5.	InVID	InVID will build a platform providing services to detect, authenticate and check the reliability and accuracy of newsworthy video files and video content spread via social media. This platform will enable novel newsroom applications for broadcasters, news agencies, web pure-players, newspapers and publishers to integrate social media content into their news output without struggling to know if they can trust the material or how they can reach the user to ask permission for re-use. It will ensure that verified and rights-cleared video content is readily available for integration into breaking and developing news reports.	www.invid-project.eu

Table 22 : Description of other EU funded projects collaborated with COMRADES in Y3

5.4 Direct contact with stakeholders (*face to face meetings*)

5.4.1 List of face to face meetings with stakeholders

No.	Partner	Name & type of contact	Date of meeting	Venue/Location of the meeting
1.	TUD	Red Cross IFRC	Oct. 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia
2.	TUD	UN OCHA	Oct. 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia
3.	TUD	Unicef	Oct. 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia
4.	TUD	University of Indonesia	Oct. 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia
5.	TUD	Petabencana	Oct. 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia
6.	TUD	Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Indonesia	Nov. 2018	Jakarta, Indonesia
7.	TUD	FloodTags	Nov. 2018	The Hague, Netherlands
8.	TUD	Cordaid	Nov. 2018	The Hague, Netherlands
9.	TUD	Red Cross NL	Nov. 2018	The Hague, Netherlands

10.	OU	Nesta, UK	Dec 6, 2018	Digital Innovation workshop, ICT2018 Vienna
11.	OU	NARLabs, Taiwan	Dec 5, 2018	ICT2018 Vienna
12.	OU	webLyzard, Austria	Dec 4, 2018	ICT2018 Vienna
13.	OU	SINTEF Digital, Norway	Dec 5, 2018	ICT2018, Vienna
14.	OU	UNESCO	Dec 5, 2018	ICT2018, Vienna
15.	OU	THALES, France	Dec 6, 2018	ICT2018, Vienna
16.	OU	ENGINEERING, Italy	Dec 4, 2018	ICT2018, Vienna

Table 23 : List of face to face meetings with stakeholders

5.4.2 Highlights of face to face meetings with stakeholders

Our partners from the TU Delft made several meeting in Jakarta and presented the COMRADES tools.

Figure 37 : Field tests in Jakarta with the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) Indonesia

Figure 38 : Guest lecture in University of Indonesia

5.5 Media coverage

5.5.1 List of COMRADES press & media coverage

This list presents all references around COMRADES made in press such as newspapers, newsletters, magazines and so on and third party media such as websites, webpages, blogs, social media (*official accounts*). The types of these items are press releases, articles, interviews, posts etc. The term of “third party media” includes all the communication channels that are not related with either the COMRADES project or the project partners.

No.	Partner	Type <i>(press release, interview, etc.)</i>	Title	Media <i>(where it was published)</i>	URL <i>(if available)</i>
1.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES in the Greek press & media	CAPSSI website	https://capssi.eu/comrades-in-the-greek-press-media/
2.	Gov2u	Article	Ushahidi COMRADES platform monitors the Kenyan Elections	CAPSSI website	https://capssi.eu/ushahidi-comrades-platform-monitors-the-kenyan-elections/
3.	Gov2u, OU	Article	COMRADES	Digital Social Innovation Website	https://digitalsozial.eu/project/2724/comrades

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4.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES papers	Clarity project website	https://clarity-csa.eu/resources
5.	Gov2u	Facebook Post	Presentation of the COMRADES paper Classifying Crises-Information...	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps-sieu/posts/938528719685524
6.	Gov2u	Facebook Post	The #press & #media in #Greece really embraced the Comrades project!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps-sieu/posts/935764783295251
7.	Gov2u	Facebook Post	The Comrades partners gave an #interview to the Athens News Agency...	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps-sieu/posts/931964210341975
8.	Gov2u	Facebook Post	The 3 rd Comrades #Newsletter Issue is out!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps-sieu/posts/890506721154391
9.	Gov2u	Facebook Post	The Comrades Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES)...	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps-sieu/posts/864697327068664
10.	Gov2u	Facebook Post	Comrades public #deliverable "D3.1 Multilingual content processing...	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps-sieu/posts/845138359024561
11.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	Athens News Agency – Macedonian Press Agency website (ΑΘΗΝΑΪΚΟ – ΜΑΚΕΔΟΝΙΚΟ ΠΡΑΚΤΟΡΕΙΟ ΕΙΔΗΣΕΩΝ)	http://www.anna.gr/home/article/259200/Comrades-I-platforma-pou-tha-boitha-tous-polites-na-diacheirizontai-kriseis
12.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να	Macedonian News Agency (ΜΑΚΕΔΟΝΙΚΟ)	http://www.anna.gr/macedonia/article/259204/Comrades-I-platforma-pou-

			διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	ΠΡΑΚΤΟΡΕΙΟ ΕΙΔΗΣΕΩΝ)	tha-boitha-tous-polites-na-diacheirizontai-kriseis
13.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις, όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς	Left.gr	https://left.gr/news/comrades-i-platforma-poy-tha-voitha-toys-polites-na-diaheirizontai-kriseis-opos-plimmyres-kai
14.	Gov2u	Interview	Καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα από Έλληνες που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς	Zougla.gr	http://www.zougla.gr/perivallon/article/kenotoma-platforma-apo-elines-pou-voitha-polites-na-diachirizonte-foties-ke-sismous
15.	Gov2u	Interview	Έλληνες δημιούργησαν καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς	iefimerida.gr	http://www.iefimerida.gr/news/417898/ellines-dimioyrgisan-kainotoma-platforma-poy-voitha-polites-na-diaheirizontai-foties-kai
16.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς	toxwni.gr	http://www.toxwni.gr/kainotomia/195670-comrades-i-platforma-poy-boitha-tous-polites-na-diacheirizontai-kriseis-opos-plimmires-kai-seismous
17.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να	circogreco.gr	https://www.circogreco.gr/2018/05/27/comrades-h-platforma-

			διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις		poy-tha-voitha-tous-polites/
18.	Gov2u	Interview	Έλληνες πίσω από την πλατφόρμα που βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς	The Caller website	https://thecaller.gr/tech/ellines-piso-apo-tin-platforma-pou-voitha-tous-polites-na-diaxeirizontai/
19.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	NOOZ. Website	http://www.nooz.gr/tech/1495561/comrades-i-platforma-poy-boitha-polites-na-diacheirizontai-kriseis
20.	Gov2u	Interview	Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	parallaxi magazine	http://parallaximag.gr/life/technologia/platforma-pou-tha-voitha-tous-polites-na-diacheirizontai-kriseis
21.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις, όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς	enallaktikos.gr	http://www.enallaktikos.gr/ar40138el-comrades-i-kainotoma-platforma-poy-tha-voitha-toys-polites-na-diaxeirizontai-kriseis-opws-plimmyres-kai-seismoys.html
22.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις, όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς	ingossip.gr	http://www.ingossip.gr/paraxena/874080-comrades-i-kainotoma-platforma-pou-tha-voitha-tous-polites-na-diachirizontai-krisis-opos-

					plimmires-kai-sismous
23.	Gov2u	Interview	«COMRADES» Έλληνες δημιούργησαν καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	Matrix24 website	http://www.matrix24.gr/2018/05/ellines-dimiourgisan-kenotoma-platfoma-pou-voitha-polites-na-diachirizonte-krisis/
24.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	ekriti.gr	http://www.ekriti.gr/tehnologia/comrades-i-platfoma-poy-tha-voitha-toys-polites-na-diaheirizontai-kriseis
25.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	palo.gr	http://www.palo.gr/ygeia/comrades-i-platfoma-poy-tha-voitha-toys-polites-na-diaheirizontai-kriseis/17996471/
26.	Gov2u	Interview	Πλατφόρμα από Έλληνες βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς	Pelop.gr	http://www.pelop.gr/?page=article&DocID=459312&srv=10
27.	Gov2u	Interview		news123.gr	https://bit.ly/2ylmj8f
28.	Gov2u	Interview	Καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα από Έλληνες που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς	Newslog.	http://www.newslog.gr/art/4361364/kainotoma-platfoma-apo-ellines-pou-voitha-polites-na-diaheirizontai-fwties-kai-seismous

29.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	Marketpost.gr	https://marketpost.gr/technology/comrades-platforma-kriseis/34086/
30.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η Πλατφόρμα Που Θα Βοηθά Τους Πολίτες Να Διαχειρίζονται Κρίσει	Analitis.gr	https://analitis.gr/comrades-h-platforma-poy-tha-bohtha-toys-polites-na-diaxeirizontai-kriseis/
31.	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις, όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς	BOPEINH website	http://www.vorini.gr/teleytaia-nea/comrades-i-platforma-pou-tha-voitha-tous-polite/
31	Gov2u	Interview	Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις	FORTUNE 60reece.gr website	http://www.fortunegreece.com/article/comrades-i-platforma-pou-tha-voitha-tous-polites-na-diachirizonte-krisis/
32.	Gov2u	Interview		newsone.gr	http://newsone.gr/texnologia/1768516-ellines-dimiourgisan-kainotoma-platforma-pou-voitha-polites-na-diachirizontai-foties-kai-sismous
33.	Gov2u	Interview	Καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα από Έλληνες που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται	ASTRA TV	https://bit.ly/2libGs3

			φωτιές και σεισμούς		
34.	Gov2u	Interview	Ελληνες δημιούργησαν καινοτόμα πλατφόρμα που βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς	i-Tech News	https://bit.ly/2tjyiDU
35.	Gov2u	Interview	ΕΛΛΗΝΕΣ ΔΗΜΙΟΥΡΓΗΣΑΝ ΚΑΙΝΟΤΟΜΑ ΠΛΑΤΦΟΡΜΑ ΠΟΥ ΒΟΗΘΑ ΠΟΛΙΤΕΣ ΝΑ ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΖΟΝΤΑΙ ΦΩΤΙΕΣ ΚΑΙ ΣΕΙΣΜΟΥΣ	Activenews.gr	http://activenews.gr/ελληνες-δημιουργησαν-καινοτομα-πλατ/
36.	Gov2u	Interview	«Ηλεκτρονικό σωσίβιο» για φυσικές καταστροφές	Dimokratia newspaper (Εφημερίδα Δημοκρατία) sheet no. 2.183	
37.	Gov2u	Interview	«Ηλεκτρονικό σωσίβιο» για φυσικές καταστροφές	Dimokratia newspaper (Εφημερίδα Δημοκρατία) <i>online version</i>	http://www.dimokratianews.gr/content/86780/ilektroniko-sosivio-gia-fysikes-katastrofes
38.	Gov2u	Article	Liaisons	POWER project website	https://www.power-h2020.eu/our-network/liaisons/
39.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES interview on Action24 TV	CAPSSI website	https://capssi.eu/comrades-interview-on-action24-tv/
40.	Gov2u	TV live Interview		Action 24 TV channel (TV	http://action24.gr/ekpompes-

				news show "Today")	on-demand/today/today-28-6-2018/ (view from 27:43 to 35:49)
41.	Gov2u	Article	Collaboration between COMRADES and PLASTIC twist projects	CAPSSI website	https://capssi.eu/collaboration-between-comrades-and-plastic-twist-projects/
42.	Gov2u	Post	Fresh Comrades synergy with PlasticTwist project!!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/964766637061732
43.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades #live broadcast from Action24 TV network!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/946669305538132
44.	Gov2u	Article	FLOOD-serv welcomes the COMRADES project to its network	FLOOD-serv website	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-welcomes-the-comrades-project-to-its-network/
45.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES Project	FLOOD-serv website	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/comrades-project/
46.	Ushahidi	Article	From earthquakes to unrest: new platform boosts community resilience in a crisis	European Commission portal	http://ec.europa.eu/research/informationcentre/article_en.cfm?&artid=48656&caller=FP
47.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades public #deliverable "D3.1 Multilingual content processing methods" is available on issuu.com	CAPSSI Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/845138359024561?_tn=-R

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48.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES) is now #available on Google Sheets Add-on ...	CAPSSI Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/864697327068664?_tn=-R
49.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades partners gave an #interview to the Athens News Agency - Macedonian Press Agency...	CAPSSI Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/931964210341975?_tn=-R
50.	Gov2u	Post	The #press & #media in #Greece really embraced the Comrades project!	CAPSSI Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/935764783295251?_tn=-R
51.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades #live broadcast from Action24 TV network!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/946669305538132?_tn=-R
52.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades #live broadcast from Action24 TV network!	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts/653741431630370?_tn=-R
53.	Gov2u	Post	Fresh Comrades synergy with PlasticTwist project!!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/964766637061732?_tn=-R
54.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades won the #award of the best #presentation at the 18th International...	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/222966455051284?_tn=-R
55.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades won the #award of the best #presentation at the 18th International	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/972048846333511?_tn=-R

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56.	Gov2u	Post	We are happy to #announce the establishment of a #cooperation among our project, the Comrades, and the FLOOD-serv Project.	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts/679268445744335?_tn=-R
57.	Gov2u	Post	Families_Share and COMRADES projects join forces	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/205971893417407?_tn=-R
58.	Gov2u	Post	The communication teams of Families_Share and Comrades are pleased to #announce...	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/223804081634188?_tn=-R
58.	Gov2u	Post	The communication teams of Families_Share and Comrades are pleased to #announce...	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts/680292368975276?_tn=-R
59.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES welcomes Crowd4Roads to its network!	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/233515747329688?_tn=-R
60.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES welcomes Crowd4Roads to its network!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/1003611459843916?_tn=-R
61.	Gov2u	Post	#Fresh Comrades video available on our #YouTube channel!	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/235411300473466?_tn=-R

62.	Gov2u	Post	The #communication_team of our project, Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos were invited by Electronic Compass as #guest_speakers	Electronic Compass Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1852002078169503&id=258269567542770&_tn_=-R
63.	Gov2u	Post	The #communication_team of our project, Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos were invited by Electronic Compass as #guest_speakers	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/242743626406900?_tn_=-R
64.	Gov2u	Post	The #communication_team of our project, Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos were invited by Electronic Compass as #guest_speakers	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/235410817140181?_tn_=-R
65.	Gov2u	Post	The #communication_team of our project, Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos were invited by Electronic Compass as #guest_speakers	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/1015835108621551?_tn_=-R
66.	Gov2u	Post	The September #Newsletter Issue of the Families_Share Project is out!	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/240576633290266?_tn_=-R
67.	Gov2u	Post	The September #Newsletter Issue of the	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/

			Families_Share Project is out!		241108983237031? tn =-R
68.	Gov2u	Post	CAPS Bytes#7 - 7th CAPSSI newsletter	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/240840983263831? tn =-R
69.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades scientific #results and all #CAPS projects' #outputs are available at Capssi EU website!	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/242486856432577? tn =-R
70.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades scientific #results and all #CAPS projects' #outputs are available at Capssi EU website!	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/241420046539258? tn =-R
71.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades scientific #results and all #CAPS projects' #outputs are available at Capssi EU website!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/1029109857294076? tn =-R
72.	Gov2u	Post	Crisis Information Processing - with the power of A.I." #Keynote delivered at the 10th #International_Conference_on_Social_Informatics	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/243305226350740? tn =-R
73.	Gov2u	Post	Crisis Information Processing - with the power of A.I." #Keynote delivered at the 10th #International_Conference_on_Social_Informatics	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/248110792536850? tn =-R

74.	Gov2u	Post	Crisis Information Processing - with the power of A.I." #Keynote delivered at the 10th #International_Conference_on_Social_Informatics	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/1033576886847373?_tn=-R
75.	Gov2u	Post	Social Innovation Community (SIC) has just launched the #Lisbon_Declaration..	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/1038285316376530?_tn=-R
76.	Gov2u	Post	Social Innovation Community (SIC) has just launched the #Lisbon_Declaration..	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/246621819352414?_tn=-R
77.	Gov2u	Post	Social Innovation Community (SIC) has just launched the #Lisbon_Declaration..	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/247187062629223?_tn=-R
78.	Gov2u	Post	The #Final_Event of Social Innovation Community (SIC) will be held in #Seville, #Spain..	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/248622662485663?_tn=-R
79.	Gov2u	Post	The #Final_Event of Social Innovation Community (SIC) will be held in #Seville, #Spain..	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/246621696019093?_tn=-R
80.	Gov2u	Post	New #contest supports #sustainable #municipal_water_concepts.	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/248622605819002?_tn=-R
81.	Gov2u	Post	New #contest supports #sustainable #	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/caps

			municipal_water co ncepts.		sieu/posts/1044 474775757584? tn =-R
82.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades featured at European Commission portal!	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/caps sieu/posts/1048 683065336755? tn =-R
83.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades featured at European Commission portal!	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/FLO ODservEU/posts /748720372132 475? tn =-R
84.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades featured at European Commission portal!	Families_Shar e Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/fami liesShare/posts/ 2505270556285 57? tn =-R
85.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES Humanitarian ChatBot	Families_Shar e Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/fami liesShare/posts/ 2505269989618 96? tn =-R
86.	Gov2u	Post	Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES)	Families_Shar e Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/fami liesShare/posts/ 2513885555424 07? tn =-R
87.	Gov2u	Post	Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES)	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/caps sieu/posts/1050 521421819586? tn =-R
88.	Gov2u	Post	Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES)	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/FLO ODservEU/posts /750332498637 929? tn =-R
89.	Gov2u	Post	SIC Final Event: " Beyond Imagination: a socially innovative Europe"	Families_Shar e Facebook Page	https://www.fac ebook.com/fami liesShare/posts/ 2524306554381 97? tn =-R

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90.	Gov2u	Post	The article from the European Commission portal about Comrades has been also featured at Capssi EU website.	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts/752573118413867?_tn=-R
91.	Gov2u	Post	The article from the European Commission portal about Comrades has been also featured at Capssi EU website.	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/253122902035639?_tn=-R
92.	Gov2u	Post	Our project expands its network and continues to support other great #EU_projects!	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts/754245161579996?_tn=-R
93.	Gov2u	Post	I-React in our related projects list! Have a look at Comrades synergies with other #EU_projects.	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsieu/posts/1058013517737043?_tn=-R
94.	Gov2u	Post	I-React in our related projects list! Have a look at Comrades synergies with other #EU_projects.	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/254940981853831?_tn=-R
95.	Gov2u	Post	I-React in our related projects list! Have a look at Comrades synergies with other #EU_projects.	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts/756543391350173?_tn=-R
96.	Gov2u	Post	30 papers in 35 months! #Impossible?? Not	FLOOD-serv Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/posts

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			for the Comrades team!		/758227061181806? tn =-R
97.	Gov2u	Post	30 papers in 35 months! #Impossible?? Not for the Comrades team!	Families_Share Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/posts/256268748387721? tn =-R
98.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades fresh collaboration with I-React and other #latest developments of our project available	CAPSSI Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capsisieu/posts/1062344330637295? tn =-R
99.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES featured at European Commission portal	CAPSSI Website	https://capssi.eu/comrades-featured-at-european-commission-portal/
100.	Gov2u	Article	H2020 RELATED PROJECTS	IREACT website	http://project.i-react.eu/stakeholders/
101.	Gov2u	Article	FLOOD-serv welcomes the COMRADES project to its network	FLOOD-serv website	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-welcomes-the-comrades-project-to-its-network/
102.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES Project	FLOOD-serv website	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/comrades-project/
103.	Gov2u	Tweet	We are glad to be in touch with fellow projects like @comradesproject. Together, we are building more resilient societies!	IREACT Twitter account	https://twitter.com/IREACT_EU/status/1064822654807535616
104.	Gov2u	Tweet	Want to see some projects similar to	IREACT Twitter account	https://twitter.com/IREACT_EU/

			ours? Pass by our Stakeholders section, where we have featured @comradesproject and many other		status/1063040750370340864
105.	Gov2u	Tweet	@comradesproject, η ευρωπαϊκή πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις, όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς	AMNA news official twitter account	https://twitter.com/amna_news/status/998545121456029696
106.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES interview on Action24 TV	CAPS Bytes newsletter Issue no.7 – October 2018	https://mailchi.mp/6ca2b96746c9/caps-bytes6-6th-capssi-newsletter-1680617?e=1b9fda6a31
107.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES in the Greek press & media	CAPS Bytes newsletter Issue no.7 – October 2018	https://mailchi.mp/6ca2b96746c9/caps-bytes6-6th-capssi-newsletter-1680617?e=1b9fda6a31
108.	Gov2u	Post	30 papers in 35 months! #Impossible?? Not for the COMRADES project team!	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6471330586668593152/
109.	Gov2u	Post	Our #communication_team, Pantelis Kanellopoulos and Vassiliki Zalavra, has created a #short_video for explaining the COMRADES..	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6465524724876353536

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110.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES project expands its network and continues to support other great #EU_projects!	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6469145430683979776
111.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES project featured at European Commission portal!	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6465169777642995712
112.	Gov2u	Post	"Crisis Information Processing - with the power of A.I." #Keynote delivered at..	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6456100391116378112
113.	OU	Post	Slides from my SocInfo 2018 keynote on the CAPS COMRADES project	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6451782527559434240
114.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES welcomes Crowd4Roads to its network	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6438026329211437056
115.	Gov2u	Post	Families_Shares and COMRADES projects join forces	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6428201397006663680
116.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES awarded at ICISO 2018	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6427818494707920896
117.	Gov2u	Post	Fresh Comrades synergy with PlasticTwist project!!	CAPSSI LinkedIn Group	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6425326157662547968

118.	Gov2u	Article	New collaborations	Plastic Twist Newsletter Issue No. 2 – Autumn 2018	
119.	Gov2u	Post	PlasticTwist Pilots are on a roll, with different events and activities	Plastic Twist Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/PlasticTwist/photos/a.393030167835172/556077091530478/?type=3&theater
120.	Gov2u	Article	Social innovation in Europe: 8 inspiring projects funded by the EU's research programme	Social Innovation Academy Website (Erasmus+ project)	http://www.socialinnovationacademy.eu/social-innovation-europe-8-inspiring-projects-funded-eu-research-programme/

Table 24 : List of COMRADES press & media coverage

5.5.2 List of COMRADES references at partners' communication channels

This list presents all the references around the COMRADES in partners' communication channels (*websites, press releases, newsletters and other media e.g. partners' social media official accounts*)

S/N	Partner	Type (press release, interview, etc.)	Title	Media (where it was published)	URL (if available)
1.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades presentation in ESWC 2018 is available at SlideShare and you can #find it at	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156539602421057?tn=-R
2.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES project published its 1 st Press Release! Check it out!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156231680856057?tn=-R

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3.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES 1 st Press Release published on issuu! Have a look!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156231830971057?_tn=-R
4.	Gov2u	Post	Our Communication s Team, Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos, gave an interesting interview about COMRADES platform..	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156460098221057?_tn=-R
5.	Gov2u	Post	So proud and happy that our COMRADES project and platform has already gained so much visibility in so many sites	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156460100476057?_tn=-R
6.	Gov2u	Post	The COMRADES May meeting	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156484950211057?_tn=-R
7.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES: The platform that helps citizens to manage crises events - Interview at the Greek news Agency ANA-MPA	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156520646336057?_tn=-R
8.	KMIOU	Post	The Comrades interview on Action24 TV featured at Capssi EU website!	KMIOU Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/KnowledgeMediaInstitute/posts/408477659558855?__tn__=-R
9.	Gov2u	Post	Our Communication s team, Vassiliki	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156460100476057?_tn=-R

			Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos, gave a second interview to the #Greek press about the Comrades project!		0156529372001057?_tn=-R
10.	Gov2u	Post	CAPSSI - COMRADES in the Greek press & media	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156534393461057?_tn=-R
11.	Gov2u	Post	The Comrades presentation in ESWC 2018 is available at SlideShare..	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156539602421057?_tn=-R
12.	Gov2u	Post	Short Video created by Gov2U team for promoting our project's results and especially the Humanitarian ChatBot tool	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156539683281057?_tn=-R
13.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades #live broadcast from Action24 TV network!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156558141676057?_tn=-R
14.	Gov2u	Post	- COMRADES #YouTube Channel -	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156566493831057?_tn=-R
15.	Gov2u	Post	Fresh Comrades synergy with PlasticTwist project!!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156609451081057?_tn=-R
16.	Gov2u	Post	Families_Share and COMRADES projects join forces	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156631274991057?_tn=-R
17.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES welcomes Crowd4Roads to its network!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156707642516057?_tn=-R

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18.	Gov2u	Post	The 7th Capssi EU newsletter #issue is out! In "CAPS stories" section you can find the Comrades #interviews in the #Greek press & media.	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156807322446057?_tn=-R
19.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades featured at European Commission portal!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156894625411057?_tn=-R
20.	Ushahidi	Post	COMRADES Humanitarian ChatBot	Ushahidi Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/ushahidi/posts/2100978986588791?_tn=-R
21.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES Humanitarian ChatBot	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156897072536057?_tn=-R
22.	Gov2u	Post	CREES provides a Web API and accessible tools for automatically..	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156902157796057?_tn=-R
23.	Gov2u	Post	The article from the European Commission portal about Comrades has been also featured at Capssi EU website.	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156912511091057?_tn=-R
24.	KMIOU	Post	30 papers in 35 months! #Impossible?? Not for the Comrades team!	KMIOU Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/KnowledgeMediaInstitute/posts/492482881158332?_tn=-R
25.	Gov2u	Post	30 papers in 35 months! #Impossible??	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10156936362396057?_tn=-R

			Not for the Comrades team!		
26.	OU	Article (OU news)	COMRADES at ICT2018	OU website	http://kmi.open.ac.uk/news/article/19013
27.	USFD	Grantham centre website	Using language to save lives	USFD website	http://grantham.sheffield.ac.uk/using-language-to-save-lives-by-diana-maynard/
28.	USFD	Grantham centre website	Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack	USFD website	http://grantham.sheffield.ac.uk/helping-crisis-responders-find-the-informative-needle-in-the-tweet-haystack/

Table 25 : List of COMRADES references

5.5.3 Highlights of Press & Media coverage

5.5.3.1 Interview at Dimokratia Newspaper

The newspaper “Dimokratia” (*Εφημερίδα Δημοκρατία*) published on the 2nd of June 2018 (*sheet no. 2.183*) the interview that Gov2u partners gave about the COMRADES project. The newspaper was the Saturday’s edition which according the official agency “Argos”, which makes the distribution of the press across Greece, that sheet sold **8,580 copies**. The data are extracted by the official website of “Argos” agency and you can find them at:

<http://www.argoscom.gr/index.php?page=17>.

However, for reader’s ease we include in this section a screenshot of this list as displayed in **figure 39**.

Επιλέξτε τύπο Κυκλοφορίας					
Ημερησίων Εφημερίδων (Πανελλαδικό) 02/06/2018 - 02/06/2018					
ΠΡΩΙΝΕΣ					
Έντυπο	Πώληση Τρέχουσας Έκδοσης	Πώληση Προηγούμενης Έκδοσης	Διαφορά	%Διαφορά	
ΚΑΘΗΜΕΡΙΝΗ	14.340	14.390	-50	0	
ΡΙΣΟΣΤΑΤΙΧΕ	5.280	5.360	-80	-1	
STAR-PRESS	4.920	4.960	-40	-1	
ΑΥΓΗ	960	1.050	-90	-9	
Ο ΛΟΓΟΣ	80	80	0	0	
Σύνολο	25.580	25.840	-260	2	
ΑΠΟΓΕΥΜΑΤΙΝΕΣ					
Έντυπο	Πώληση Τρέχουσας Έκδοσης	Πώληση Προηγούμενης Έκδοσης	Διαφορά	%Διαφορά	
ΤΑ ΝΕΑ	24.180	27.840	-3660	-13	
ΕΦΗΜΕΡΙΔΑ ΤΩΝ ΣΥΝΤΑΚΤΩΝ	15.260	16.190	-930	-6	
ESPRESSO	10.270	12.430	-2160	-17	
ΜΑΚΕΔΟ	10.000	9.620	400	4	
ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ	8.580	8.560	20	0	
ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΟΣ ΤΥΠΟΣ	5.520	5.770	760	13	
ΕΘΝΟΣ	5.020	3.260	1.760	54	
ΚΟΝΤΡΑ ΝΕWS	2.700	2.720	-20	-1	
ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΟΡΑ	2.290	2.370	-80	-3	
Σύνολο	84.650	88.760	-3.910	2	

Figure 39 : Number of Copies sold – Argos Agency

The article briefly describes what the COMRADES platform can offer to citizens as well as communities and gives few information around the project. Moreover, it mentions the challenges that nowadays societies confront due to the rising number of natural disasters and how COMRADES platform can help citizens to manage and overcome crises. Moreover, the newspaper republished the interview at its online version on the 4th of June 2018 and can be found at:

<http://www.dimokratianews.gr/content/86780/ilektroniko-sosivio-gia-fysikes-katastrofes>

Figure 40 : Interview at Dimokratia Newspaper published on 02/06/18

Figure 41 : Interview at Dimokratia Newspaper website (online version) published on 04/06/18

5.5.3.2 Interview at Athens News Agency - Macedonian Press Agency (ANA-MPA)

The COMRADES partners from Gov2u, Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos who are responsible for the communication of the project and its results gave an interesting interview to the [Athens News Agency - Macedonian Press Agency \(ANA-MPA\)](#) where they explained how the COMRADES platform can help citizens to manage and overcome crises.

Figure 42 : Interview at the news agency ANA-MPA

Figure 43 : AMNA Official Twitter account - Interview at the news agency ANA-MPA

In particular, our partners described to the reporter - by giving an example of a flood event - how the COMRADES platform identifies crisis related events via social media and “filters” the collected information in order to ensure its validity. AMNA news agency made a [tweet](#) at its official twitter account about the COMRADES interview. This account has 55,000 followers. The interview was given in Greek and can be found at:

<http://www.amna.gr/macedonia/article/259204/Comrades-I-platforma-pou-tha-boitha-tous-polites-na-diacheirizontai-kriseis>

Moreover, the topic of the project and the solution that the COMRADES platform offers to its users, attracted the attention of the Greek media. As a result, 26 media across the country republished this interview. Among them are the most popular news websites in Greece such as: **fortunegreece.gr**, **i-Tech News**, **astra TV**, **ekriti.gr**, **parallaxi magazine**, **The Caller**, **analitis.gr**, **marketpost.gr**, **iefimerida.gr**, **voreini.gr** etc. Screenshots from the mentioned above sites that republished the interview are provided below while screenshots from all medium that featured can be found in **Appendix II**. It is worth mentioning that in each site their visitors shared our interview to their personal social media profiles as can be viewed in screenshots.

Figure 44 : Collage of the most popular sites that published COMRADES interview

Figure 45 : COMRADES interview at zougla.gr

The most popular news website that re-published our interview was **zougla.gr** which according to the information that this website announced in October 2018 it is the **5th most popular website in Greece** and the **9th most popular website worldwide** in the category of breaking news. This means that COMRADES interview was under a great success and the project was communicated not only nationally (*in Greece*) but also internationally. The following figures present information and metrics¹ aforementioned about the zougla.gr news website.

Top Sites in Greece

Global By Country By Category

Site	Daily Time on Site	Daily Pageviews per Visitor	% of Traffic From Search	Total Sites Linking In
1. Google.gr Η μεγαλύτερη μηχανή αναζήτησης παγκόσμια στα ελληνικά.	6:35	10.14	0.80%	6,385
2. Google.com Enables users to search the world's information, including websites, images, and videos. Offers...More	7:52	9.01	3.30%	3,217,794
3. Youtube.com YouTube is a way to get your videos to the people who matter to you. Upload, tag and share your...More	8:51	4.92	13.80%	2,418,260
4. Facebook.com A social utility that connects people, to keep up with friends, upload photos, share links and...More	9:50	3.92	7.40%	6,415,532
5. Zougla.gr Εβδομαδιαία από την Ελλάδα και τον κόσμο. Όλα τα νέα γίνου από την Πολιτική, Οικονομία, Υγεία...More	6:41	3.52	15.10%	7,324
6. Life.gr Life.gr - Είδηση, Ανάπτυξη, Διασκέδαση, Urban Culture & Artiva με πρωτοποριακά μέσα υαση.	9:44	4.57	18.50%	5,800
7. Blogspot.com	3:13	2.41	44.80%	18,146
8. Skout24.gr Σύγκριση τιμών ηλεκτρονικών καταστημάτων.	5:41	7.55	50.80%	823

Figure 46 : zougla.gr website – 5th most popular site in Greece

¹ Source: <https://www.zougla.gr/politiki/article/media/article/ston-ourano-i-episepsimotita-tou-zouglagr>

The top 500 sites on the web

Global By Country By Category

Site	Daily Time on Site	Daily Pageviews per Visitor	% of Traffic From Search	Total Sites Linking In
1 Foxnews.com Breaking News, Latest News and Current News from FoxNews.com. Breaking news and video. Latest C...More	5:26	2.62	13.30%	72,931
2 Bloomberg.com Breaking financial, business and economic news worldwide from major provider of information ser...More	3:32	1.62	30.50%	71,819
3 Cnbc.com Headline news, articles, reports, stocks and quotes, message boards, and a stock ticker.	2:41	1.54	32.10%	36,354
4 Cbsnews.com Online news provided by television broadcast company CBS.	2:29	1.53	36.40%	56,991
5 Nbcnews.com National Broadcasting Company.	2:45	1.36	20.40%	36,375
6 Abcnews.go.com Includes American and world news headlines, articles, chatrooms, message boards, news alerts, v...More	2:42	1.36	28.70%	72,207
7 Thedailybeast.com With commentary on politics, entertainment, technology and world events. Includes pictures and ...More	2:54	1.61	13.70%	31,572
8 Dailycaller.com Features opinion, research, and entertainment	3:54	2.06	9.30%	26,670
9 Zougla.gr Ειδητογραφία από την Ελλάδα και τον κόσμο. Όλα τα νέα γύρω από την Πολιτική, Οικονομία, Υγεία...More	6:41	3.52	15.10%	7,324
10 Prnewswire.com Press release news service. Information direct from the sources.	2:05	1.56	47.40%	37,810
11 Foxbusiness.com National and international business and financial news, articles, and video reports.	2:36	1.41	10.10%	12,181

Figure 47 : zougla.gr website – 9th most popular site worldwide in the breaking news category

5.5.3.3 Interview in Action24 TV channels on a Live Broadcast

Vassiliki Zalavra and Pantelis Kanellopoulos, COMRADES partners from Gov2u and responsible for the project’s external communication and visibility, were invited at the TV news show “**Today**” by the journalist Ms. Maira Barba to talk about COMRADES project and its innovative platform. The live broadcast interview took place on the 28th of June 2016 and it was featured on Action24 TV channel at national level.

Figure 48 : Interview on a Live Broadcast in Action24 TV channel

The live interview lasted approximately 8 minutes during which Gov2u partners explained how the COMRADES platform can help citizens and communities to manage, respond to and recover

from crises events such as floods, earthquakes, hurricanes and wildfires across Europe and beyond. The interview is Greek and can be viewed directly (27:43 - 35:49) via the on demand service of the TV channel Action24 at:

<http://action24.gr/ekpompes-on-demand/today/today-28-6-2018/>.

Moreover it can be viewed at the **COMRADES YouTube channel** on:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8iOjlgNe_6I&t=34s

5.5.3.4 From earthquakes to unrest: new platform boosts community resilience in a crisis (Article at the European Commission Portal)

An article about COMRADES was featured at the European Commission portal at Success Stories section (*Research and innovation* → *Project* → *success stories*). The article described how the COMRADES platform can help communities to increase their resilience during crises events. Our partner Shadrock Roberts, from Ushahidi, briefly talked on the topic. The article can be found at:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/infocentre/article_en.cfm?artid=48656&fbclid=IwAR3tLOkulD2VgjrAYmkirt2yW7odn9-uFnxJMzfi85DeMFk8mbJL5CSXjs

Figure 49 : Article at European Commission Portal

5.5.3.5 CAPSSI website, newsletter & LinkedIn group

Throughout Y3 COMRADES was featured on the “Latest News” section of CAPSSI website where announcement about the latest developments and news of our project were made. The CAPS Bytes newsletter Issue no.7 (October 2018) communicated the COMRADES interviews in Greek press and media. Lastly, CAPSSI LinkedIn group featured our project as well as the rest of their social media accounts.

Figure 50 : CAPSSI twitter account & LinkedIn group

Figure 51 : CAPSSI website “Latest News” section

Figure 52 : CAPS Bytes newsletter issue no. 7

5.5.3.6 Plastic Twist Newsletter issue No.2 – autumn 2018

Plastic Twist is an EU funded project under the Horizon 2020 programme and fellow CAPS one. Within the frame of the communication liaisons that we have established with other European projects, Plastic Twist project featured COMRADES in its second newsletter issue.

Figure 53 : Plastic Twist project newsletter issue no. 2

5.6 Publications

No.	Title (APA style: for book - Author's Last name, F. M. (Year published). Title of book. Location of publisher: Publisher and	Link	Article in peer-reviewed journal	Article in peer-reviewed Conferences	Article in NON peer-reviewed journal	Chapter of book	Book	Other (please specify)
1.	Burel, Gregoire; Saif, Hassan and Alani, Harith (2017). Semantic Wide and Deep Learning for Detecting Crisis-Information Categories on Social Media. In: The Semantic Web – ISWC 2017.	http://oro.open.ac.uk/51726/		x				Conference paper
2.	Miriam Fernandez, Lara Piccolo, Harith Alani, Diana Maynard, Christop Meili, Meia Wippoo (2017). Pro-Environmental Campaigns via Social Media: Analysing Awareness and Behaviour Patterns	https://webscience-journal.net/webscience/article/view/44	x					
3.	Khare, Prashant; Fernandez, Miriam and Alani, Harith (2017). Statistical Semantic Classification of Crisis Information. In: 1st workshop of Hybrid Statistical Semantic Understanding and Emerging Semantics (HSSUES), 16th International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC) 2017, 21-22 Oct 2017.	http://oro.open.ac.uk/51181/						Workshop paper
4.	Fernandez, Miriam; Dickinson, Tom and Alani, Harith (2017). An analysis of UK Policing Engagement via Social Media. In: Social Informatics. SocInfo 2017 (Ciampaglia,	http://oro.open.ac.uk/51174/		x				

D6.5 Third Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

	G.; Mashhadi, A. and Yasseri, T. eds.), Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer, pp. 289–304.							
5.	Derczynski, Leon et al. “Results of the WNUT2017 Shared Task on Novel and Emerging Entity Recognition.” NUT@EMNLP (2017).	http://aclweb.org/anthology/W17-4418						Workshop paper
6.	Ahmet Aker, Leon Derczynski and Kalina Bontcheva (2017). Simple Open Stance Classification for Rumour Analysis. Proceedings of Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing, pages 31–39, Varna, Bulgaria, Sep 4–6 2017.	http://acl-bg.org/proceedings/2017/RANLP%202017/pdf/RANLP005.pdf			x			Conference paper
7.	Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Noisy User-generated Text	http://aclweb.org/anthology/W17-44						Workshop proceedings
8.	Isabelle Augenstein, Leon Derczynski, Kalina Bontcheva (2017). Generalisation in Named Entity Recognition: A Quantitative Analysis. In: Journal Computer Speech and Language Volume 44 Issue C, July 2017 pp 61-83	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csl.2017.01.012		x				
9.	Ahmet Aker, Johann Petrak and Firas Sabbah (2017). An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer. Proceedings of Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing, pages 40–45, Varna, Bulgaria, Sep 4–6 2017	http://acl-bg.org/proceedings/2017/RANLP%202017/pdf/RANLP006.pdf						x

10.	Vittorio Nespeca, Kenny Meesters, & Tina Comes. (2018). Evaluating Platforms for Community Sense-making: Using the Case of the Kenyan Elections. In Kees Boersma, & Brian Tomaszewski (Eds.), ISCRAM 2018 Conference Proceedings – 15th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (pp. 924–934). Rochester, NY (USA): Rochester Institute of Technology	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324162897_Evaluating_Platforms_for_Community_Sensemaking_Using_the_Case_of_the_Kenyan_Elections_Vittorio_Nespeca							Conference paper
11.	Burel, Gregoire and Alani, Harith (2018). Crisis Event Extraction Service (CREES) - Automatic Detection and Classification of Crisis-related Content on Social Media. In: 15th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management, 20-23 May 2018, Rochester, NY, USA.	http://oro.open.ac.uk/55139/							Conference paper
12.	Derczynski, Leon & Meesters, Kenny & Bontcheva, Kalina & Maynard, Diana. (2018). Helping Crisis Responders Find the Informative Needle in the Tweet Haystack. Proceedings of the 15th ISCRAM Conference – Rochester, NY, USA May 2018	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322787706_Helping_Crisis_Responders_Find_the_Informative_Needle_in_the_Tweet_Haystack							Conference paper
13.	Khare, Prashant; Burel, Gregoire and Alani, Harith (2018). Classifying Crises-Information Relevancy with Semantics. In: Extended	http://oro.open.ac.uk/54361/							Conference paper

D6.5 Third Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

	Semantic Web Conference (ESWC) 2018, 3-7 Jun 2018, Heraklion, Crete.							
14.	Piccolo, Lara; Meesters, Kenny and Roberts, Shadrock (2018). Building a Socio-technical Perspective of Community Resilience with a Semiotic Approach. In: Proceedings of 18th International Conference on Informatics and Semiotics in Organisations (ICISO) 2018, Springer.	http://oro.open.ac.uk/54703/						Conference paper
15.	Piccolo, Lara; Roberts, Shadrock; Iosif, Anna and Alani, Harith (2018). Designing Chatbots for Crises: A Case Study Contrasting Potential and Reality. In: Proceedings of the British HCI Conference, 4-6 Jul 2018, Belfast, ACM.	http://oro.open.ac.uk/55325/						Conference paper
16.	Piccolo, Lara; Mensio Martino; Alani, Harith (2018). Chasing the Chatbots: Directions for Interaction and Design Research. In: Proceedings of INSCI 2018 - International Workshops CONVERSATIONS, 26-Oct, St. Petersburg, Springer (in press).	http://oro.open.ac.uk/id/eprint/57382						Workshop paper
17.	Dungs, Sebastian., Aker, Ahmet, Fuhr, Norbert, & Bontcheva, Kalina (2018). Can Rumour Stance Alone Predict Veracity?. In Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics (pp. 3360-3370).	http://www.aclweb.org/anthology/C18-1284						Conference paper

18.	Abby Muricho Onencan, Kenny Meesters, Bartel Van de Walle: Methodology for Participatory GIS Risk Mapping and Citizen Science. In: Citizen Science and Earth Observation (2018)							Under review
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Table 26 : List of publication Y3

6 Overview of WP6 activities in Y3

6.1 Performance of WP6 activities

The current section provides an overview of the communication and dissemination tools and activities used and respectively performed from the January 2018 to December 2018 (Y3). **Table 27** briefly provides all the information presented in previous sections of the current document.

<i>Type of Tool or Activity</i>	<i>Measurement Unit</i>	<i>Number</i>
COMRADES website	Pageviews	20,960
	Sessions (<i>visits</i>)	3,181
	Users (<i>unique visitors</i>)	1,924
Social media	New Facebook page likes	34 (24.64% increase)
	New Twitter followers	95 (30.75% increase)
	New LinkedIn connections	98 (34.96% increase)
Newsletter	Number of issues published	1
Press release	Number of press releases published	1
Digital Publishing Platforms	Number of platforms deployed	3
	Items uploaded at Scribd	3
	Views at Scribd	53
	Items uploaded at Issuu	6
	Impressions at Issuu	1,255
	Items uploaded at SlideShare	5
	Views at SlideShare	599
Outreach activities	Events organized	9
Interviews	Total interviews	3
	Interview on TV	1
	Interview in Press	2
Press & Media coverage	References in press & media	120

Third party events	Participation & presentation of the project in third party events	10
Collaboration with other project	Established collaborations with EU funded projects & other initiatives (<i>CAPS project included</i>)	8
	Established collaborations with CAPS projects	3
Publications	Number of publications	18
YouTube Channel	Videos uploaded	4
	Total views	182

Table 27 : Overview of WP6 activities in Y3

7 Conclusions

This document constitutes an annual report on the communication and dissemination activities made by the COMRADES consortium within the period January 2018 – December 2018 (Y3). Additionally, the communication tools that were used under the same period, the actions related with them and their performance is also presented.

The effectiveness of the communication tools was measured continuously throughout Y3 and their results were evaluated by the communication and dissemination team of the COMRADES project.

During the third year, we made further efforts to promote the project and its results and maximize its visibility not only to target groups but also to the general public across Europe and beyond. In quantitative terms regarding the reporting period (*January 2018 – December 2018*), COMRADES had 18 publications, 8 established synergies with other EU funded projects, 9 outreach activities, 10 presentations in third party events, 1 interview on Greek TV channel (*live broadcast from Action24 channel*), 2 interviews in Greek press (*in “Dimokratia” newspaper and ANA-MPA news agency*) and more than 26 news websites in Greece republished these interviews while a hundred references from all across Europe were occurred about COMRADES in other websites (e.g. European Commission’s portal), blogs and so on.

In qualitative terms, the project was really embraced by the audience wherever and whenever it was presented by the consortium in workshops, conferences, press and media which helped us to further promote our results, meet all the communication goals that we had set, and in many cases exceed them.

APPENDIX I – Google Analytics (All Web Site Data)

Figure 54 : All Web Site Data (Google Analytics)

APPENDIX II – COMRADES interview in ANA-MPA republished in Greek media (screenshots)

Figure 55 : marketpost.gr

Figure 56 : zougla.gr

Figure 57 : toxoni.gr

Figure 58 : iefimerida.gr

The screenshot shows the website **left.gr** with a search bar and navigation menu. The main article is titled "Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις, όπως πλημμύρες και σεισμούς". Below the article is a photo of a man and a woman looking at a laptop. To the right is a sidebar with a list of recent posts under the heading "ΠΡΟΣΦΑΤΑ ΔΗΜΟΦΙΛΗ".

Figure 59 : left.gr

The screenshot shows the website **CIRCOGRECO** with a navigation menu and a search bar. The main article is titled "Comrades: Η πλατφόρμα που θα βοηθά τους πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται κρίσεις". Below the article is a photo of a man and a woman looking at a laptop. To the right is a weather widget for Athens and a sidebar with a list of recent posts under the heading "ΕΙΔΗΣΕΟΓΡΑΦΙΑ".

Figure 60 : circogreco.gr

Figure 61 : thecaller.gr

Figure 62 : nooz.gr

Figure 63 : voreini.gr

Figure 64 : fortunegreece.com

Figure 65 : astratv.gr

Figure 66 : itechnews.gr

Figure 67 : parallaximag.gr

Figure 68 : enallaktikos.gr

Figure 69 : matrix24.gr

Figure 70 : ekriti.gr

analitis.gr
 “Δεν υπάρχει μεγαλύτερη χαρά από το να αισθάνεται κανείς δημιουργός. Ο θρίαμβος της ζωής εκφράζεται με τη δημιουργία. Henri Bergson, 1859-1941, Γάλλος φιλόσοφος.”

ΕΙΔΗΣΕΙΣ

Ειδήσεις

Comrades: Η Πλατφόρμα Που Θα Βοηθή Τους Πολίτες Να Διαχειρίζονται Κρίσεις

21 Μάιος 2018

6 SHARES

Πάνω σε μια νέα καινοτόμο πλατφόρμα που έχει ως στόχο να βοηθή πολίτες σε στιγμές κρίσης και αποτελεί μέρος ευρωπαϊκού έργου, εργάζονται δύο νέοι, η Βασιλική Ζαλαβρά και ο Παντελής Κανελλόπουλος. Το έργο COMRADES ή αλλιώς Collective Platform for Community Resilience and Social Innovation during Crises, όπως είναι η πλήρης ονομασία του, είναι ένα Ευρωπαϊκό πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας τριετούς διάρκειας.

«Κύριος στόχος του έργου είναι να αναπτύξει μια καινοτόμο πλατφόρμα που θα συλλέγει και θα επεξεργάζεται πληροφορίες σε πραγματικό χρόνο για γεγονότα κρίσεων (όπως σεισμούς, τυφώνες, πλημμύρες, κ.α) που μπορεί να πλήξουν μια κοινότητα και οι οποίες αναρτώνται από τους πολίτες στα διάφορα κοινωνικά δίκτυα πληροφόρησης. Ταυτόχρονα, η πλατφόρμα δεν περιορίζεται στη συλλογή και ανάλυση των πληροφοριών αυτών, αλλά και στην επαλήθευση της αυθεντικότητάς τους. Ως αποτέλεσμα, ενισχύεται η κοινοτική ανεκτικότητα και οι ιδίες πλέον οι κοινότητες μπορούν μέσω της σωστής και έγκυρης πληροφόρησης να εκτιμήσουν την κρίση, να επικοινωνήσουν μεταξύ τους και να αυτο-οργανωθούν τους τρόπους και τα μέσα αντιμετώπισης της», τονίζει μιλώντας στο ΑΠΕ-ΜΠΕ η Βασιλική Ζαλαβρά, διευθύντρια και υπεύθυνη επικοινωνίας και υλοποίησης Ευρωπαϊκών Προγραμμάτων Gov2u.

Η συγκεκριμένη πλατφόρμα αποτελεί ουσιαστικά ένα μηχανισμό που συμβάλλει στη διαχείριση κρίσεων σε έντονα καταστάσεις, όπως είναι για παράδειγμα τα ακραία καιρικά φαινόμενα (πλημμύρες, τυφώνες, κλπ), σεισμούς και φωτιές.

«Ένα πλημμυρικό φαινόμενο εμφανίζεται σε μια περιοχή και πολλοί κάτοικοι έχουν ανάγκη από βοήθεια για να απεγκλιβθούν από τα σπίτια τους από τις ομάδες διάσωσης. Ταυτόχρονα όμως προκύπτουν ανάγκες για βοήθεια σε

ΡΟΗ ΕΙΔΗΣΕΩΝ

- 12:33 Ανεξαρτητοποιήθηκε ο δημοτικός σύμβουλος Δ.Ράπτης
- 12:33 Η συγκλονιστική δραματική ιστορία του Σιγκ Τζοφινγκ
- 12:27 Αντιμέτωποι με τον ... «βιβλιοφάγο» θα έρθουν όσοι επισκεφτούν την Πλατεία Κοτζιά το Σάββατο
- 12:27 Στις 16 Μαρτίου η κλήρωση του Παγκοσμίου Κυπέλλου
- 12:25 Ευκαιρία για τη Μπάγερν, φοβηρί για την Πρόκριση η Τσέλσι
- 12:24 Ανακάλυψη της ΝΔ με ασαφή αναφορά του πρωθυπουργού σε «καρπούζι της ΝΔ»
- 12:24 Σε σχέδια του Ρέντοσ Πιάνο η νέα γέφυρα στη Γένοβα

ΠΙΟ ΔΙΑΒΑΣΜΕΝΑ

- Πολιτική
Γ. Ραγκούσης: Το σύστημα θα παίξει τα ρέστα του στην προσπάθεια να πείσει η κυβέρνηση στις Πρέσβεις
- Πολιτική
Νέο σχήμα ρύθμισης οφελών για τα ασφαλιστικά ταμεία προανγγέει η Έφη Αχτσιόγλου
- Πολιτική
Στ. Κούλογλου: Μεγάλη τιμή για την χώρα μας η πρόταση για την υποψηφιότητα Τσίπρα για Νόμπελ Ειρήνης
- Ειδήσεις
Στ. Κούλογλου: Μεγάλη τιμή για την χώρα μας η πρόταση για την υποψηφιότητα Τσίπρα για Νόμπελ Ειρήνης
- Ειδήσεις
Νέα τροπολογία Αβελανίτη του κόμματος Ζάεφ: Η υπερκοιτίδα δεν καθορίζει ούτε προεκρίνει την εθνότητα

ΧΡΗΜΑΤΙΣΤΗΡΙΟ

Ελλάδα Κόσμος Τάση Οικονομίας

Figure 71 : analitis.gr

Τρίτη 18 Δεκεμβρίου 15:54
 5°-13° Πάτρα

ΜΙΚΡΕΣ ΑΓΓΕΛΙΕΣ | ΒΙΒΛΙΟΠΛΕΙΟ | ΕΦΗΜΕΡΙΔΑ | VIDEO | ΑΝΑΖΗΤΗΣΗ

pelop.gr
 Ενταξίωση στην Εφημερίδα «ΠΕΛΟΠΟΝΝΗΣΟΣ»

Αρχική | Τοπικά & Κοινωνία | Αθλητικά | Ελλάδα | Κόσμος | Auto - Moto | Πολιτική | Οικονομία | Πολιτισμός | Επιστήμη & Τεχνολογία | Υγεία & Διατροφή
 Τέντες: All Around | Γαστρονομία | Αγορά | Αγγλία | Βιβλίο | Le Zanda | Ισπάλιον | Φιλοξενούμενοι | Εργασία | Τrip | Ζωδια | Faces & Life | Γυναικά

► Μάιος 2019: Ο δρόμος προς τις κάλπες ► ΔΗΜΕΡΙΔΑ "Μιλώμε για την πόλη"

Επιστήμη & Τεχνολογία

23/05/2018 [02:00]

Πλατφόρμα από Έλληνες βοηθά πολίτες να διαχειρίζονται φωτιές και σεισμούς

Πάνω σε μια νέα καινοτόμο πλατφόρμα που έχει ως στόχο να βοηθά πολίτες σε στιγμές κρίσης και αποτελεί μέρος ευρωπαϊκού έργου, εργάζονται δύο νέοι, η Βασιλική Ζαλαβρά και ο Παντελής Κανελλόπουλος.

Το έργο COMRADES ή αλλιώς Collective Platform for Community Resilience and Social Innovation during Crises, όπως είναι η πλήρης ονομασία του, είναι ένα Ευρωπαϊκό πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας τριετούς διάρκειας.

«Κύριος στόχος του έργου είναι να αναπτύξει μια καινοτόμο πλατφόρμα που θα συλλέγει και θα επεξεργάζεται πληροφορίες σε πραγματικό χρόνο για γεγονότα κρίσεων (όπως σεισμούς, τυφώνες, πλημμύρες, κ.α) που μπορεί να πλήξουν μια κοινότητα και οι οποίες αναρτώνται από τους πολίτες στα διάφορα κοινωνικά δίκτυα πληροφόρησης. Ταυτόχρονα, η πλατφόρμα δεν περιορίζεται στη συλλογή και ανάλυση των πληροφοριών αυτών, αλλά και στην επαλήθευση της αυθεντικότητάς τους. Ως αποτέλεσμα, ενισχύεται η κοινοτική ανεκτικότητα και οι ιδίες πλέον οι κοινότητες μπορούν μέσω της σωστής και έγκυρης πληροφόρησης να εκτιμήσουν την κρίση, να επικοινωνήσουν μεταξύ τους και να αυτο-οργανωθούν τους τρόπους και τα μέσα αντιμετώπισης της», τονίζει μιλώντας στο ΑΠΕ-ΜΠΕ η Βασιλική Ζαλαβρά, διευθύντρια και υπεύθυνη επικοινωνίας και υλοποίησης Ευρωπαϊκών Προγραμμάτων Gov2u.

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Figure 72 : pelop.gr

Figure 73 : palo.gr

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